

D10.5 Final Plan of Use and Dissemination of Results and Communication Activities

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1.0			

Executive summary

The **final Plan of Use and Dissemination of Results** presented here details the dissemination and communication efforts, delineates the exploitation plan and describes the agreement on exploitation among Fatigue4Light partners.

The current document, prepared with the inputs and contributions provided by all the consortium members, offers a summary of the identified results establishing the basis for potential scale-up, exploitation and commercialisation, and describes the main communication and dissemination strategies carried out to facilitate market uptake as well as to transfer research results and knowledge towards the scientific and industrial community.

In terms of exploitation, the document offers a comprehensive overview of exploitable results, as well as the intellectual property rights (IPR) of each partner. A thorough analysis of key results has been conducted in collaboration with partners, considering market trends, barriers, and customer requirements associated with each key outcome.

In regard to dissemination and communication, this deliverable showcases the Fatigue4Light's communication and dissemination activities produced and the impact achieved. It encompasses the dissemination and visibility of project outcomes through scientific articles published, participation in exhibitions and conferences aimed at presenting the results to academic and industrial stakeholders, as well as the organisation of webinars and workshops. In addition, it highlights direct dissemination efforts with European associations and involvement in clustering activities at the EU level.

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List of abbreviations

<i>AEDP</i>	<i>Spanish Data Protection Agency</i>
<i>EV</i>	<i>Electric Vehicles</i>
<i>GDPR</i>	<i>General Data Protection Regulation</i>
<i>IPR</i>	<i>Intellectual Property Rights</i>
<i>KER</i>	<i>Key Exploitable Result</i>
<i>KPI</i>	<i>Key Performance Indicator</i>
<i>T</i>	<i>Task</i>
<i>VCI</i>	<i>Visual Corporate Identity</i>
<i>WP</i>	<i>Work Package</i>

Introduction

Fatigue4Light in a nutshell:

The Fatigue4Light project, with a duration of three years, has developed **innovative tests and computer simulation methodologies** with the goal to predict the lifespan of Electric Vehicle chassis components and to optimize material selection for enhanced performance.

The project has worked on the **application of new materials adapted to chassis requirements**, such as advanced high-strength steels, special automotive stainless steels, high-strength aluminum alloys and metal-polymer hybrid materials. The main innovation of the project expects to **reduce the weight of the vehicle chassis up to 30%**, taking into account aspects of eco-design and circular economy.

Attainment of the objectives and explanation of deviations

The deliverable is fully in line with the contractual obligations and the project objectives. There is no time and content deviation.

1.1 Objectives of the deliverable

The **D10.5 Final Plan of Use and Dissemination of Results and Communication Activities** serves as a comprehensive report detailing all project activities. It aims to document and provide reference information related to exploitation and intellectual property rights (IPR) for the benefits of partners. This report also outlines the communication and dissemination of project research, activities and outcomes, useful to support exploitation and ensure market uptake.

This deliverable is included as part of the WP10 Dissemination & Exploitation whose broad goals are:

- To **plan and carry out a dissemination strategy** to facilitate market uptake and transfer research results and knowledge towards the scientific, academia and industrial community.
- To **set up the main Fatigue4Light communication channels and ensure a continuous communication of the project activities** in order to generate awareness on the project.
- To **ensure proper management of the exploitable results** to accelerate its market introduction.
- To **facilitate the acceptance and use of the results** by the market through using standards and standardisation.

This document is presented as a report of all the actions carried out since the beginning of the project in tasks **10.1 Dissemination Activities**, **10.2 Communication Activities** and **10.3 Exploitation Activities**, all coordinated by Eurecat. It is an update of the initial interim PUDR deliverable presented in M18.

The document is structured in two main sections:

1. **Exploitation Plan (EP)**: this part includes the main conclusions derived from T10.3, involving the creation of an exploitation strategy detailing the project's exploitable results and gathering input from the consortium on potential exploitation pathways.

2. **Dissemination & Communication Plan and management:** compiling dissemination and communication done from M1 – M36 (February 2021 - January 2024), including the participation in key events, webinars organisation, scientific publications produced, project's website performance and social media activity among others.

2. Final Exploitation Plan

The Exploitation Plan, which derives from the Exploitation Activities Task (10.3.), is designed to maximize the full impact of Fatigue4Light developments and prepare the transition towards market uptake to fully achieve the expected impact. The Exploitation Plan of the PUDR describes the activities that should be undertaken (how and by whom) in order to ensure the exploitation/use of results beyond the project itself and provides a guide to capitalize the commercialization efforts that should be done for that. This exploitation strategy is built up as a result of sound analysis of potential users, market agents, and external environment.

Fatigue4Light consortium is quite diverse as it gathers 13 different partners, including technology centres, universities, standardization bodies and businesses:

- Centre Internacional de Mètodes Numèrics en Enginyeria (CIMNE)
- Fundació Eurecat (EUT)
- Centro Ricerche Fiat SCPA (CRF)
- Lulea Tekniska Universiteit (LTU)
- MW Italia S.R.L. (MW)
- Arcelormittal Maizieres Research, S.A. (AMMR)
- Gestamp Hardtech AB (GES)
- Politecnico di Torino (POLITO)
- RISE Sicomp AB, (RISE)
- Profilglass S.p.A. (Profilglass)
- Composite Service Europe AB (CSE)
- Asociación Española de Normalización (UNE)
- Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC)

All the partners of Fatigue4Light are interested in the results exploitation in different manners. Research partners are more oriented to transfer knowledge and technology to interested stakeholders while the consortium SMEs and large enterprises are strongly focused on commercialization of the derived research instruments, products and processes.

The methodology for creating the final Use of Results part of the PUDR has been the following:

- Identification and definition of Fatigue4Light exploitable results, including Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) management.
- Definition of individual exploitation plan for each of the results.
- Definition of the common exploitation approach.

2.1 Identification of exploitable results and IPR claims

Fatigue4Light has resulted in several exploitable results. Through intense collaboration with all the Partners, these results have all been identified and add up to a total of 16 results. Results have been classified in 5 main interconnected categories:

1. **Know-how:** Practical knowledge, skills, and expertise that are not easily codified or documented
2. **Software:** Computer programs and their associated documentation
3. **Procedure:** A set of steps or a sequence of actions that need to be followed to accomplish a specific task or achieve a particular result.
4. **Services:** Intangible offerings provided by individuals or entities
5. **Material:** Tangible substances or substances that can be physically touched or measured.

In order to develop this Plan of Use of Results, a BFMULO methodology in the form of a table has been developed. This table has compiled both exploitation intentions of each Partner (further explained further in the document) and Intellectual Property claims of each Partner, which can be found in the table below. This table includes:

- **Name of the exploitable result:** Exploitable result identified by the Partners themselves.
- **Project Partners involved:** what Partners have participated in the achievement of the result.
- **IP Claims:** Intellectual Property claims that the involved partners have in each particular result. It can include:
 1. **IPR's on Background information (B):** Information, excluding foreground information, brought to the project from existing knowledge, owned or controlled by project Partners in the same or related fields of the work carried out in the research project.
 2. **IPR's on Foreground information (F):** Information including all kind of exploitable results generated by the project Partners or 3rd parties working for them in the implementation of the research project, and type of participation in the achievement of the result. To claim ownership on a foreground information, it is necessary for a Partner to have a task (s) in the project related to that very result, contributing to the achievement of it.
- **How is the Partner involved?:** Explanation of the role of the Partner in its IP Claims

Table 1: Explanation of the role of the Partners in its IP Claims

KER number	Name of the exploitable result	Project Partners involved	IP CLAIMS	How is the Partner involved?
1	Fatigue numerical model	CIMNE	B,F	They brought a previous version of the model in previous publications (B), and they are improving extensions of the model based on the work done in the project (F)
		CRF	B,F	They brought CRF methodology to simulate fatigue behavior (B) and they're participating in the developing of new methodology to predict fatigue behavior (F)
		LTU	B,F	Contribution of know-how regarding fatigue modelling from previous projects (B) contribution of the fatigue model itself, through the improvement of the model (F)

		MW	B,F	MW has a model that can possibly contribute to the final model (B), they are going to improve our own model for the project (F)
		RISE	B,F	Delivery of fatigue related properties and parameters of FRP and Fiber Metal Laminates for use as input data in numerical models (B). They are improving an internal model based on work done in the project (F)
		UPC	F	They bring data to run fatigue simulations (F)
2	Fatigue modelling software	CIMNE	B,F	They brought a previous version of the software (B) and they are continuing to improve it (F). The fatigue model is programmed in Kratos Multiphysics open-source FE code, written in Python and C++.
		CRF	B	We brought CRF information about current software that they are using (B)
		RISE	B,F	The fatigue model is currently written in m-code (MatLab, Octave) and work as a stand-alone tool (B). However, to increase model efficiency and connection to FE-simulations they are considering to implement it as a subroutine to LSDyna or Abaqus (F).
3	Methodology to optimize mass savings in fatigue dimensioning parts	CIMNE	F	They are developing the conclusions of all the work they are doing and developing the main guidelines regarding reducing weight (F)
		EUT	F	They are developing new methods to evaluate relevant material's properties for fatigue dimensioned components (F)
		CRF	B,F	They brought CRF current methodology to evaluate lightweight design (B), they will apply the new methodology to our vehicle to evaluate the mass reduction (F)
		MW	B	On WP4 they are carrying tests that a partner might use to develop this result (B)
		GES	B,F	They bring know-how when it comes to dimensioning parts (B), they are designing a demonstrator (F)
		Profilglass	B,F	Expertise in aluminum field, and specific ways to use aluminum (B) and participation on the activity (F)

4	Experimental approach for fast fatigue evaluation of materials based on temperature evolution	CRF	B,F	They brought current staircase methodology to predict the fatigue (B), together with the other partners they are putting together the state-of-art (F)
		UPC	F	They bring data to run fatigue simulations (F)
		AMMR	B	Background on self-heating measurements, they will use for fast-fatigue characterisation of the materials (B)
5	Experimental approach for fast fatigue evaluation of materials based on stiffness evolution	EUT	B,F	EUT developed the stiffness method in a previous H2020 Formplanet project (B). It is expected to improve it to be more reliable and extract more material information from a single test (F). The patented method can be licensed (L) or commercialized as a service (M)
		MW	B	On WP4 they are carrying tests that a partner might use to develop this result (B)
6	Ultrasonic VHCF tests to assess material defectiveness	CRF	B,F	They brought current staircase methodology to predict the fatigue (B), together with the other partners they are putting together the state-of-art (F)
		POLITO	B,F	Ultrasonic fatigue tests have performed in the past on cylindrical specimens (B). The testing methodology has been extended also to sheet specimens (F).
7	Statistical modelling and prediction of fatigue performance	CRF	B,F	They brought current staircase methodology to predict the fatigue (B), together with the other partners they are putting together the state-of-art (F)
		UPC	F	They bring data to run fatigue simulations (F)
		POLITO	B,F	Statistical analysis of fatigue data according to international standards (B). Proposal of an innovative statistical model to deal with size effects in fatigue (F).

		EUT	B,F	They brought previous knowledge on how to predict the fatigue behaviour of materials based on fracture toughness and existing defects (B). Additional models and data treatment will be developed for lightweight materials(F)
8	New methodology with accelerated fatigue testing strategies coupled with fast fatigue life calculation	EUT	B,F	They brought the knowledge that they developed in a previous H2020 Formplanet project (B), and they will set it to be applied to more materials and conditions. The data obtained is expected to allow a fast approximation of the component's fatigue life (F).
		CRF	B,F	They brought current staircase methodology to predict the fatigue (B), together with the other partners they are putting together the state-of-art (F)
		LTU	B,F	Contribution of know-how by fatigue life calculations from previous projects (B) contribution of the activity itself by fatigue life calculations (F)
		CIMNE	B,F	They brought the fatigue modelling software (B), they are co-defining alongside EUT the potential services of this initiative (F)
		UPC	F	They bring data to run fatigue simulations (F)
		MW	B,F	They are making test with our patented bent specimen (B,F) to improve fast assessing of grades for dimensioning wheels
		AMMR	F	They are comparing several method for fast-fatigue evaluation, they contribute on finding better methodologies, they could find this new methodology (F)
		9	Model to predict the fatigue life of formed parts	CIMNE
EUT	B,F			They brought previous knowledge on how to predict the fatigue behaviour of components considering the mechanical properties of the material and forming procedures (B). The models will be improved to capture the key points that determine the fatigue behaviour of the component.(F)

		UPC	F	They bring data to run fatigue simulations (F)
		LTU	B,F	Contribution of know-how regarding fatigue and shear cutting modelling from previous projects (B) contribution of the fatigue model itself, through the improvement of the model (F)
		AMMR	F	They are comparing several method for fast-fatigue evaluation, they contribute on finding better methodologies, they could find this new methodology (F)
		MW	B,F	MW has a model that can possibly contribute to the final model (B), they are going to improve our own model for the project (F)
10	A manufacturing method for forming and co-curing multi-material components	RISE	B,F	Know how on tool design (B). Tool design and methodology for pressing and co-curing composite to metal (F)
		Profilglass	B,F	Expertise in aluminum field, and specific ways to use aluminum (B) and participation on the activity (F)
11	Pre-impregnation method for fiber reinforcement	RISE	B,F	Know how on pre-impregnation of fibre reinforcement (B). RISE and CSE have developed a methodology for making prepregs using Selcom EBX 400 NCF glass reinforcement and the Huntsman ARALDITE LY1564 resin (F).
		CSE	F	CSE has manufactured b-staged laminated based on the methodology proposed by RISE (F)
12	AHSS grades with improved fatigue resistance	MW	B,F	Based on current knowledge of processing material (B) they will adapt our process through simulation and tests (F)
		AMMR	B,F	Some of the materials tested in the projects are ours (B), they could find ways to improve fatigue resistance by comparing the results they have obtained in the project on all the materials (F)
		UPC	F	They bring data to run fatigue simulations (F)
13	Al alloys grades with improved fatigue resistance	Profilglass	F	Based on knowledge on aluminum mechanical properties, they improved know-how on fatigue issues to select and propose compositions suitable for fatigue applications (F)

		UPC	F	They bring data to run fatigue simulations (F)
14	New hybrid metal-composite with improved fatigue resistance	Profilglass	B,F	Expertise in aluminum field, and specific ways to use aluminum (B) and participation on the activity (F)
		CSE	B	They have a long experience in drywinding of composite fibers and they think they can use this knowledge in combination with other materials in order to develop the hybrid concept (B)
15	New wheel produced with high strength steel-grades	MW	B,F	They brought the knowledge on wheel production (B), they develop the wheel itself (F)
16	Method for structural health monitoring by embedded sensors	RISE	B,F	Provided background in fiber-optical sensor technology for composites. Developed and verified method for integration in FRP-hybrid material

2.2 Identified Exploitable Results

In the following sections, we will delve into these identified key exploitable results (KERs), exploring the potential they hold for both commercial and research-driven exploitation. Each result has been obtained through an extensive interview with each partner, where we obtained information about their exploitation interests, their innovative status and IPR issues, among others. Each result has been individually validated with each partner and collectively with the whole Consortium, guaranteeing the conformity of all the members with the final results.

Creating a detailed business plan for each of the exploitable results of Fatigue4Light presents a unique challenge due to the diverse interest and objectives of the project Partners. With numerous Partners involved, each result has varying implications for different entities, ranging from academic publications to internal use for process improvement. This diversity in interest and use goals complicates the formulation of a conventional business plan that typically revolves around a specific market analysis, commercialization strategies, and revenue projections. Given the multifaceted nature of the project, the overarching approach is to provide specific information for each of the individual results, and finally combining with an aggregated overview of Fatigue4Light project from a business perspective. This allows for a holistic understanding of the project without delving into individual, partner-specific business strategies in which there are multiple confluences of interests.

For the individual analysis of each of the results, the information on the results has been distributed on an individual table containing the following information:

KER #: Name and number of the Key Exploitable Result

Main Partner: Partner who has claimed the lead in the development of the KER.

Other partners involved: Partners that have also been involved in the development of the KER.

Category: KER Category type according to the IPR (previously explained)

Description: General description of the KER and its features.

Unique Value Proposition: Explanation on what makes the KER different and/or superior to its present competitors in the market.

Competitors: Present and potential competitors that are in the market and that could present alternatives that could compete with the KER.

Time to Market: Time that will take for the KER to be in the market, in months since the beginning of the project.

Initial TRL: TRL in which the KER was at the beginning of the project.

Final TRL: TRL in which the KER is at the end of the project.

Potential target: Market, sectors and industries in which the KER could have a place. While Fatigue4Light was originally conceived for the automotive industry, the exploitable results obtained during the development of the project are applicable to other potential markets that might be of interest for the Partners.

Individual Exploitation Interests: Interests of each Partner in the exploitation of the KER.

Potential Exploitation Agreements: Potential agreements needed to ease the joint exploitation of the KER. Here we suggest agreements for each result that could be necessary to improve the efficiency in exploitation. These agreements are not the only ones that could be applied to each result and Partners have been welcomed to explore those formulas that suit their interests best.

IPR strategy: Intellectual Property Rights strategy advised, thus, how the KER should be protected.

IPR Strategy Rationale: Reasons on why that particular IPR strategy has been advised.

Table 2: Key Exploitable Results (KERs) of Fatigue4Light

KER #1: Fatigue numerical model	
Main partner	CIMNE
Other partners involved	CRF, LTU, MW, RISE, UPC
WP(s) involved	3,4
Category	Know-how
Description	A validated mathematical model to predict the structural behavior of parts subjected to cyclic loads
Unique Value Proposition	Track crack propagation on components after complex loading histories that can comprise hundreds of thousands of cycles of different types of cyclic and monotonic loads.
Competitors	<p>1.Commercial Finite Element Analysis (FEA) Software Companies: Companies that specialize in providing FEA software (such as Abaqus, ANSYS, and MSC software), may have fatigue analysis modules that compete.</p> <p>2.Material testing and simulation companies: Companies like Instron and MTS Systems Corporation that focus on material testing and simulation may offer solutions that include fatigue analysis capabilities.</p> <p>3.Other research institutions and academia: Other research institutions and universities may develop and offer their fatigue analysis models as part of academic research or through technology transfer programs</p> <p>4.Engineering Consulting Firms: Consulting firms with expertise in structural analysis and fatigue assessment may develop their in-house tools or use commercial software to provide similar services to the fatigue numerical model</p>
Time to Market	M40

Initial TRL	5
Final TRL	7
Potential target	<p>1. Automotive industry: to optimize the design of automotive components for enhanced durability and safety.</p> <p>2. Aerospace and aviation: To assess the fatigue life of aircraft components, ensuring the structural integrity and reliability of aerospace structures.</p> <p>3. Materials manufacturing: To enhance the fatigue performance of their products.</p> <p>4. Energy and power generation: To predict and optimize the fatigue performance of structural elements in companies involved in energy production.</p> <p>5. Machinery and equipment manufacturing: To improve the fatigue resistance of components, leading to longer product lifespans.</p> <p>6. Research and Development: to use the model for advanced studies and experimentation.</p>
Individual interests	Exploitation
	<p>CIMNE aims to make academic publications on this result and offer potential consulting services with this model to the industry.</p> <p>CRF aims to use these results internally to create a further product in the future.</p> <p>LTU aims make academic publications on this result.</p> <p>MW aims to use these results internally to improve other processes.</p> <p>RISE aims to use the model for internal processes and potentially offer consulting services with this model to the rest of the industry.</p> <p>UPC aims to make academic publications on this result.</p>
Potential agreements	exploitation
	<p>1. Joint Ownership agreement: All partners contribute to the development and refinement of the model. In this agreement, the partners jointly own the intellectual property rights of the model, defining the responsibilities and contributions of each partner, and potentially agreeing on revenue-sharing arrangements if the software is offered for commercial use, such as consulting services to the industry, as some partners intend to.</p> <p>2. Collaborative Research and Development Agreement: Partners CIMNE, LTU and UPC, who aim to publish academic papers, can agree to collaborate on joint research papers, sharing data and insights. This agreement can outline how the academic publications will be authored and credited.</p> <p>3. Exclusive Consulting Services Agreement: CIMNE and RISE, who aim to offer consulting services with the model, can establish a separate agreement defining the terms for providing these services to the industry. This agreement should cover pricing, revenue sharing, and responsibilities related to consulting services.</p> <p>4. Commercialization and product development agreement: If CRF or MW decide to create a product based on the model, they can establish an agreement regarding product development, distribution, and any potential revenue-sharing arrangements.</p> <p>5. Data Sharing and Collaboration Agreement: All the participating partners can agree on validating and improving the model continuously. This agreement should outline the terms for data sharing, joint research, and collaboration efforts.</p>

IPR strategy	Patent
IPR strategy rationale	The know-how involves a proprietary process, making it suitable for a patent. The patent should ensure to cover all the aspects that make the know-how unique.
KER #2: Fatigue modelling software	
Main partner	CIMNE
Other partners involved	CRF, RISE
WP(s) involved	3
Category	Software
Description	An upgraded software that uses the fatigue numerical model to provide an accurate and reliable prediction of fatigue performance
Unique Value Proposition	Perform nonlinear fatigue simulation on an Open-Source Platform with 0 licensing cost.
Competitors	<p>1.Commercial Finite Element Analysis (FEA) Software Companies: Companies that specialize in providing FEA software (such as Abaqus, ANSYS, and MSC software), may have fatigue analysis modules that compete.</p> <p>2.Material testing and simulation companies: Companies like Instron and MTS Systems Corporation that focus on material testing and simulation may offer solutions that include fatigue analysis capabilities.</p> <p>3.Other research institutions and academia: Other research institutions and universities may develop and offer their fatigue analysis models as part of academic research or through technology transfer programs</p> <p>4.Specialized Structural Analysis Software: Software that could include fatigue analysis features, such as SAP2000 or STAAD.</p> <p>5.Integrated Computer-Aided Engineering Plaforms: CAEs that include fatigue analysis capabilities, such as Simcenter by Siemens or Altair Hyperworks</p> <p>6.Industry-Specific simulation software providers: Providers of simulation tools that include fatigue analysis, such as nCode and LMS Virtual.Lab</p>
Time to Market	M48
Initial TRL	4
Final TRL	7
Potential target	<p>1.Automotive industry: to optimize the design of automotive components for enhanced durability and safety.</p> <p>2.Aerospace and aviation: To assess the fatigue life of aircraft components, ensuring the structural integrity and reliability of aerospace structures.</p> <p>3.Materials manufacturing: To enhance the fatigue performance of their products.</p> <p>4.Energy and power generation: To predict and optimize the fatigue performance of structural elements in companies involved in energy production.</p> <p>5.Machinery and equipment manufacturing: To improve the fatigue resistance of components, leading to longer product lifespans.</p> <p>6.Research and Development: to use the model for advanced studies and experimentation.</p>
Exploitation interests	<p>CIMNE aims to use this software internally for further activities and offer potential consulting services with this model to the industry.</p> <p>CRF is involved in this result but does not expect to make any exploitation claim on this result.</p>

	<p>RISE aims to keep the software for internal processes and potentially offer consulting services with this model to industry.</p>
Potential exploitation agreements	<p>1. Joint Ownership Agreement: All Partners (CIMNE, CRF, RISE) collectively contribute to the development and refinement of the software. In this agreement, the partners could jointly own the intellectual property rights to the software. The agreement should define the responsibilities and contributions of each partner in terms of software development, maintenance and support, and agree on revenue-sharing arrangements if the software is offered for commercial use, such as consulting services, as CIMNE and RISE intend to do.</p> <p>2. Non-Exclusive Licensing Agreement: The partners can sign an agreement to grant non-exclusive licenses to the software to each other. This allows each partner to use the software for their internal processes as needed. The licensing terms can include provisions for updates and support, ensuring the software remains accurate and reliable.</p> <p>3. Exclusive Consulting Services Agreement: CIMNE and RISE, who aim to offer consulting services with the software, can establish a separate agreement defining the terms for providing these services to the industry. This agreement should cover pricing, revenue sharing, and responsibilities related to consulting services.</p> <p>4. Non-Disclosure Agreement: Partners may consider entering into an NDA to protect sensitive information related to the software, ensuring that any confidential data, algorithms, or methodologies are safeguarded</p> <p>5. Data Sharing and Collaboration Agreement: The partners can agree to collaborate on validating and improving the software continuously. This agreement should outline the terms for data sharing, joint research and collaboration efforts.</p>
IPR strategy	Copyright
IPR strategy rationale	Copyright protection is well-suited for protecting the unique code and expression of the fatigue modelling software. It provides automatic protection upon creation, covering the specific lines of code, algorithms, and the software's architecture.

KER #3 Methodology to optimize mass savings in fatigue dimensional parts	
Main partner	CIMNE
Other partners involved	EUT, CRF, MW, GES, Profilglass
WP(s) involved	8
Category	Procedure
Description	Faster and easier procedure to optimize part lightweight
Unique Value Proposition	A multi-criteria analysis leading to finding the best component solution in terms of compromise between weight saving, mechanical performance, eco-design and economic considerations.
Competitors	<p>1. Finite Element Analysis (FEA) Software companies, such as Abaqus by Dassault Systèmes or Ansys, that provide software with optimization features</p> <p>2. Topology optimization software providers: like Altair OptiStruct, specialized in topology optimization to achieve lightweight designs</p>

	<p>3.Engineering consulting firms: Firms with expertise in structural optimization and lightweighting.</p> <p>4.Integrated Computer-Aided Engineering Platforms: CAEs such as Simcenter or Hyperworks that offer solutions based on optimization tools</p> <p>5.Other research institutions and academia: Other research institutions and universities may develop and offer their methodologies for optimizing structural mass based on fatigue considerations as part of academic research or through technology transfer programs</p>
Time to Market	M40
Initial TRL	3
Final TRL	6
Potential target	<p>1.Automotive Industry: Vehicle manufacturers and suppliers can use the methodology to optimize the design of automotive components, achieving mass savings without compromising structural integrity</p> <p>2.Aerospace and aviation: Aerospace companies can apply the methodology to reduce the weight of aircraft components, leading to fuel efficiency improvements and increased payload capacity</p> <p>3.Energy and Power Generation: Companies involved in energy production can utilize the methodology to optimize the design for structural components, enhancing efficiency and durability</p> <p>4.Civil engineering and infrastructure: Construction companies and civil engineering firms can apply the methodology in the design of bridges, buildings and other infrastructure projects</p> <p>5. Heavy machinery and equipment manufacturing: manufacturers can benefit from optimizing the mass of components, leading to improved performance and reduced energy consumption</p> <p>6. Defense and Military Applications: Defense contractors and military organizations can apply the methodology to optimize the design of components in military vehicles, aircraft, and infrastructure.</p> <p>7. Research and development: Research institutions and laboratories focused on structural engineering and optimization can use the methodology for advanced studies and experimentation.</p>
Exploitation interests	<p>CIMNE plans use it for potential activities in the future such as project workshops</p> <p>EUT will offer this methodology as a service for companies</p> <p>CRF plans to keep the methodology for internal uses mainly</p> <p>MW will keep it for internal uses</p> <p>GES will keep the methodology to use it internally to develop other products</p> <p>Profilglass has interests on commercializing this</p>
Potential agreements	<p>1.Non-Exclusive Licensing Agreement: CIMNE, EUT, CRF, MW and GES could agree to grant each other non-exclusive licenses for the use for the methodology. The licensing terms can specify how the methodology can be used, how the information can be disclosed (NDA), including for internal processes, future projects, and services for external companies. The agreement should also include provisions for updates and support to ensure the methodology remains effective and up-to-date.</p>

	<p>2. Service Provision Agreement: EUT, which plans to offer the methodology as a service, can establish a service provision agreement with the other partners, outlining the terms and conditions for providing this service to companies, including pricing, revenue sharing, and responsibilities.</p> <p>3. Internal use Agreement: CRF, MW, and GES can enter into an agreement to define how the methodology will be implemented within their organizations. This agreement may include terms related to data sharing, updates, and collaboration on further developments or applications of the methodology.</p> <p>4. Commercialization Agreement: Profilglass, with a specific interest in commercializing the methodology, can discuss a commercialization agreement with the other partners, addressing terms related to pricing, revenue sharing, marketing, and intellectual property rights.</p> <p>5. Data Sharing and Collaboration Agreement: All partners can enter into a collaborative agreement for continuous improvement and development of the methodology. This agreement can outline the terms for data sharing, joint research, and collaborative efforts to enhance the methodology.</p>
IPR Strategy	Trade Secret/Patent
IPR Strategy Rationale	The methodology involves a proprietary process, making it suitable for trade secret protection. As the methodology involves a combination of processes that contribute to its uniqueness, trade secret is the best strategy here. It can evolve into a patent in the future.

KER #4: Experimental approach for fast fatigue evaluation of materials based on temperature evolution	
Main partner	AMMR
Other partners involved	CRF, UPC
WP(s) involved	2
Category	Procedure
Description	Fast and reliable test to estimate fatigue limit for metals and FRP.
Unique Value Proposition	Results are delivered within hours instead of weeks and by using a reduced amount of material.
Competitors	As all 3 involved partners that have expressed interest in exploiting this result want to keep it for internal uses or academic purposes, the competitors would be those companies that have already incorporated a method to estimate a fast evaluation of the fatigue of their materials.
Time to Market	M42
Initial TRL	5
Final TRL	7
Potential target	As all 3 involved partners that have expressed interest in exploiting this result want to keep it for internal uses or academic purposes, the target would be the scientific community.
Exploitation interests	<p>AMMR aims to use it internally to create other products</p> <p>CRF aims to keep it for internal uses</p> <p>UPC aims to make academic publications on this result</p>
Potential exploitation agreements	1. Non-Exclusive licensing agreement: CRF, UPC and AMMR can enter into a non-exclusive licensing agreement

	<p>that allows each partner to use the methodology for their internal purposes. The licensing terms can specify how the methodology can be used and include provisions for updates and support.</p> <p>2.Internal Use Agreement: CRF and AMMR, who primarily intend to use the methodology internally, can establish an agreement to define how the methodology will be implemented within their organizations. This agreement may include terms related to data sharing, updates and collaboration on further developments or applications.</p> <p>3.Collaboration and Joint Product Development Agreement: AMMR, with an interest in creating other products with the approach, can collaborate with CRF and potentially UPC to explore the development of new products or services. This agreement can outline the responsibilities and revenue-sharing arrangements related to the creation and commercialization of new products.</p>
IPR Strategy	Patent
IPR Strategy Rationale	As the methodology involves a combination of processes that contribute to its uniqueness, patent is the best strategy here. No trade secret can be developed since UPC aims at publishing.

KER #5: Experimental approach for fast fatigue evaluation of materials based on stiffness evolution	
Main partner	EUT
Other partners involved	MW
WP(s) involved	2
Category	Procedure
Description	Fast and reliable test to estimate fatigue limit for metals and FRP.
Unique Value Proposition	Results are delivered within hours instead of weeks or months and by using a reduced amount of material.
Competitors	<p>1.Traditional fatigue testing laboratories: Established materials testing laboratories that offer traditional fatigue testing services using conventional methods</p> <p>2.Advanced materials testing companies: Companies specializing in advanced materials testing and characterization</p> <p>3.Automated testing equipment providers: Manufacturers producing automated testing equipment and systems.</p> <p>4.Innovative testing technologies: Companies developing and offering alternative technologies for rapid fatigue evaluation</p> <p>5. Research institutions and universities: Academic institutions conducting research on advanced materials testing and fatigue evaluation, potentially offering competing methodologies</p>
Time to Market	M42
Initial TRL	4
Final TRL	6
Potential target	<p>1.Automotive industry: manufacturers can use the fast fatigue evaluation approach to quickly assess the fatigue performance of materials used in automotive components, ensuring durability and safety.</p> <p>2.Aerospace and aviation: aerospace companies can apply the approach to rapidly evaluate the fatigue properties</p>

	<p>of materials used in aircraft components, reducing development cycles and improving reliability.</p> <p>3. Energy and power generation: companies in the energy sector can use the approach for quick fatigue assessments of materials in critical components</p> <p>4. Materials manufacturing: companies producing materials for various applications can offer fast fatigue evaluation as a service to their clients, helping them optimize material selection.</p> <p>5. Consumer goods and electronics: manufacturers of consumer products and electronic devices can use the approach to assess the fatigue performance of materials in their products quickly</p> <p>6. Construction and infrastructure: construction companies can benefit from quickly assessing the fatigue properties of materials used in infrastructure projects, ensuring longevity and safety.</p> <p>7. Defense and military applications: defense contractors and military organizations can apply for the approach for rapid fatigue evaluations of materials used in military vehicles, equipment, and structures</p> <p>8. Engineering consulting firms: firms specializing in materials testing and analysis can offer the fast fatigue evaluation approach as a service to clients in various industries.</p> <p>9. Automated testing and quality control: integration of the approach into automated testing systems and quality control processes for industries requiring stringent material performance standards.</p>
Exploitation interests	<p>EUT aims to exploit the result through licensing or commercializing it as a service.</p> <p>MW aims to keep the result for internal uses.</p>
Potential exploitation agreements	<p>1. Licensing and Service Provision Agreement: EUT, which wants to use the approach for licensing or offering it as a service, can enter into an agreement with MW. In this agreement, EUT may acquire a license to use the methodology for commercial purposes; this can include licensing fees and terms for service provision.</p> <p>2. Non-Exclusive Licensing Agreement: MW may agree to grant a non-exclusive license to EUT for the use of the methodology for commercial purposes; the licensing can specify how EUT can use the methodology and how MW wants to use it as well in an internal way.</p> <p>3. Collaboration and Joint Product Development Agreement: EUT and MW can collaborate to explore the development of new products or services based on the methodology. This agreement can outline the responsibilities and revenue-sharing arrangements related to the creation and commercialization of new products.</p>
IPR Strategy	Trade secret/Patent
IPR Strategy rationale	<p>The methodology involves a proprietary process, making it suitable for trade secret protection. As the methodology involves a combination of processes that contribute to its uniqueness, trade secret is the best strategy here. It can evolve into a patent in the future.</p>

KER #6: Ultrasonic VHCF tests to assess material defectiveness	
Main partner	POLITO
Other partners involved	CRF
WP(s) involved	2
Category	Service
Description	New R&D service to the industry that delivers a rapid, reliable and cheap method for defect inspection
Unique Value Proposition	Results are obtained in less than an hour, instead of several hours. Post-processing of data is not needed.
Competitors	As all 2 involved partners that have expressed interest in exploiting this result want to keep it for internal uses or academic purposes, the competitors would be those companies that have already incorporated a method for defect inspection internally.
Time to Market	M48
Initial TRL	3
Final TRL	5
Potential target	As all 2 involved partners that have expressed interest in exploiting this result want to keep it for internal uses or academic purposes, the target would be the scientific community.
Exploitation interests	POLITO will publish about the service on international academic journals. CRF will keep the methodology for internal uses
Potential exploitation agreements	1.Internal Use and Academic Collaboration Agreement: This Agreement between CRF and POLITO can outline how the methodology will be used internally by CRF and simultaneously collaborate on joint research projects to provide academic insights; the agreement can specify how data, research findings, and academic publications are shared.
IPR Strategy	Patent
IPR Strategy rationale	As the methodology involves a combination of processes that contribute to its uniqueness, patent is the best strategy here. No trade secret can be developed since POLITO aims at publishing.

KER #7: Statistical modelling and prediction of fatigue performance	
Main partner	POLITO
Other partners involved	CRF, UPC, EUT
WP(s) involved	2
Category	Software
Description	New software for industries to design fatigue dimensioning parts
Unique Value Proposition	Probabilistic fatigue life and strength can be directly estimated from the results of the finite element models. Defect size population is also considered in the estimation.
Competitors	1.Materials testing and analysis firms: established companies specializing in materials testing and analysis, offering traditional methods for fatigue prediction 2.Data analytics and machine learning companies: companies leveraging advanced data analytics and machine learning techniques to predict material fatigue properties

	<p>3. Research institutions and universities: academic institutions conducting research on statistical modeling for fatigue prediction, potentially offering competing methodologies</p> <p>4. Engineering simulation software providers: companies offering simulation software for engineering applications, including fatigue prediction features</p> <p>5. Quality control and inspection solutions providers: companies providing comprehensive quality control solutions, including those incorporating statistical models for fatigue assessment</p>
Time to Market	M48
Initial TRL	2
Final TRL	4
Potential target	<p>1. Automotive industry: manufacturers can use statistical models to predict fatigue performance in vehicle components, ensuring safety and durability</p> <p>2. Aerospace and aviation: aerospace companies can apply the modelling to predict fatigue life in aircraft materials, reducing maintenance costs and improving reliability</p> <p>3. Energy and power generation: companies in the energy sector can benefit from predicting fatigue performance in material components</p> <p>4. Materials manufacturing: manufacturers producing materials for various applications can leverage statistical models to optimize material formulations and predict fatigue behavior</p> <p>5. Consumer goods and electronics: manufacturers of consumer products and electronic devices can use statistical modeling to predict the fatigue life of materials in their products</p> <p>6. Research and development: research institutions and laboratories focused on materials science can adopt statistical models for fatigue prediction in their studies and experiments.</p> <p>7. Construction and infrastructure: construction companies can use statistical modeling to predict fatigue behavior in materials used in infrastructure projects</p> <p>8. Defense and military applications: defense contractors and military organizations can apply statistical modeling to predict fatigue performance in materials used in military equipment and structures.</p>
Exploitation interests	<p>POLITO will make academic publications on the result in international academic journals.</p> <p>CRF will keep the accelerating fatigue test methodology for internal uses</p> <p>UPC aims to make academic publications on this result.</p> <p>EUT aims to exploit the analysis methodology through licensing, commercializing it as a service, and/or keeping it for internal uses</p>
Potential exploitation agreements	<p>1. Non-exclusive licensing and Service Provision Agreement: EUT, which aims to commercialize the software, can enter into a non-exclusive licensing agreement with UPC and POLITO. In this agreement, EUT may acquire a license to use and commercialize the software as a service, while UPC and POLITO can also retain the right to publish research findings in academic journals. The licensing terms can outline how the software can be used, including</p>

	<p>provisions or updates, support, and exclusivity arrangements.</p> <p>2.Academic Collaboration and Publication Agreement: UPC and POLITO can collaborate on academic research related to the software, sharing insights and findings. They can enter into a collaboration agreement to outline the terms of this academic collaboration, specifying how data, research findings and academic publications are shared.</p> <p>3.Internal Use and Commercialization Agreement: CRF and EUT can collaborate to explore the development of new products or services based on the software; the agreement can outline the responsibilities and revenue-sharing arrangements related to the creation and commercialization of new products and services.</p>
IPR Strategy	Copyright
IPR Strategy Rationale	Copyright protection is well-suited for protecting the unique code and expression of the software. It provides automatic protection upon creation, covering the specific lines of code, algorithms, and the software's architecture.

KER #8: New methodology with accelerated fatigue testing strategies coupled with fast fatigue life calculation	
Main partner	CIMNE
Other partners involved	EUT, LTU, CRF, UPC, MW, AMMR
WP(s) involved	2
Category	Procedure
Description	Validated methodology against industrial dimensioning cases
Unique Value Proposition	We deliver to the interested industrial companies a full comprehensive fatigue study (experimental- numerical) on geometries of interest with the purpose of new material deployment ensuring optimal fatigue performance
Competitors	<p>1.Accelerated fatigue testing equipment manufacturers: Companies specializing in the development and manufacturing of equipment designed for accelerated fatigue testing</p> <p>2.Materials testing and analysis firms: established companies providing traditional methods for fatigue testing and life calculation</p> <p>3.Automated testing solutions providers: companies offering automated testing solutions with a focus on accelerated fatigue testing and rapid fatigue life calculation</p> <p>4.Data analytics and machine learning companies: Entities leveraging advanced data analytics and machine learning techniques to predict fatigue life quickly based on accelerated testing data</p> <p>5.Other research institutions and universities: academic institutions conducting research on accelerated fatigue testing methods and fast fatigue life calculation, potentially offering competing methodologies</p>
Time to Market	40
Initial TRL	3
Final TRL	7
Potential target	1.Automotive industry: manufacturers can use the accelerated fatigue testing methodology to quickly assess the fatigue life of materials used in vehicle components

	<p>2. Aerospace and aviation: aerospace companies can apply the methodology to rapidly evaluate the fatigue properties of materials used in aircraft components</p> <p>3. Energy and power generation: Companies in the energy sector can benefit from rapid fatigue assessment for critical components</p> <p>4. Materials manufacturing: manufacturers producing materials for various applications can offer accelerated fatigue testing as a service, helping clients optimize material selection</p> <p>5. Consumer goods and electrics: manufacturers of consumer products and electronic devices can use the methodology to assess the fatigue life of materials in their products quickly</p> <p>6. Construction and infrastructure: construction companies can use the methodology to quickly assess the fatigue behavior of materials used in infrastructure projects</p> <p>7. Defense and military applications: defense contractors and military organizations can apply the methodology for rapid fatigue evaluations of materials used in military vehicles, equipment, and structures</p>
<p>Exploitation interests</p>	<p>EUT aims at licensing the patented method and strategy</p> <p>CIMNE intends to use the methodology as consulting services</p> <p>LTU aims to make academic publications on this result</p> <p>CRF might keep the accelerating fatigue test methodology for internal uses</p> <p>UPC aims to make academic publications on this result</p> <p>MW aims to keep the methodology for internal use to improve their own methodology</p> <p>AMRR plans to keep it internally and use it to create other products,</p>
<p>Potential exploitation agreements</p>	<p>1. Licensing agreement: EUT, with an interest in licensing the patented method and strategy, can enter into a licensing agreement with the other partners (CRF, MW, AMMR). The licensing terms can specify how EUT can use and license the methodology for commercial purposes; while CRF, MW and AMMR can retain the right to use the methodology for internal purposes.</p> <p>2. Consulting Services Agreement: CIMNE can enter into an agreement with partners who intend to use the methodology internally; this agreement would allow CIMNE to provide consulting services related to the methodology in the industry.</p> <p>3. Academic Collaboration and Publication Agreement: LUT and UPC, which aim to make academic publications on the result, can collaborate on academic research and publications. They can enter into an agreement that outlines the terms of their academic collaboration, data sharing, and publication rights.</p> <p>4. Collaboration for Product Development: AMMR, which intends to use the methodology to create other products, can collaborate with partners to explore the development of new products or services based on the methodology. This agreement can outline the responsibilities and revenue-sharing arrangements related to the creation and commercialization of new products.</p>

IPR Strategy	Patent
IPR Strategy Rationale	As the methodology involves a combination of processes that contribute to its uniqueness, patent is the best strategy here. No trade secret can be developed since LTU and UPC aim at publishing.

KER #9: Model to predict the fatigue life of formed parts	
Main partner	CIMNE
Other partners involved	EUT, UPC, LTU, AMMR, MW
WP(s) involved	4
Category	Know-how
Description	Validated model against industrial cases
Unique Value Proposition	Fatigue formulation that evaluates the nonlinear effects caused by forming processes and takes them into account in the posterior fatigue behavior
Competitors	<p>1. Finite Element Analysis (FEA) Software Providers: Companies offering FEA software that includes fatigue life prediction capabilities for formed parts</p> <p>2. Material testing and analysis firms: Established firms providing traditional methods for fatigue testing and life prediction, potentially considered competitors if they offer similar predictive modeling services</p> <p>3. Engineering simulation software providers: Companies offering simulation software for engineering applications, including fatigue life prediction features for formed components</p> <p>4. Automated design and optimization software providers: Entities developing software tools that integrate predictive models for fatigue life into the materials design and optimization process</p> <p>5. Research institutions and universities: Academic institutions conducting research on predictive modeling for fatigue life prediction in formed components, potentially offering competing methodologies.</p>
Time to Market	40
Initial TRL	4
Final TRL	7
Potential target	<p>1. Automotive industry: manufacturers can use the predictive model to estimate the fatigue life of formed parts used in vehicles, ensuring durability and safety</p> <p>2. Aerospace and aviation: Aerospace companies can apply the model to predict the fatigue properties of formed parts in aircraft, contributing to the design and maintenance of structural components</p> <p>3. Manufacturing and metalworking: companies involved in metal forming and manufacturing can benefit from the predictive model for optimizing the design and production of formed parts</p> <p>4. Construction and infrastructure: Construction companies can use the model to estimate the fatigue life of formed structural components in buildings and infrastructure projects.</p> <p>5. Energy and power generation: Companies in the energy sector can apply the model for predicting fatigue life in formed parts of machinery and equipment.</p> <p>6. Consumer goods and electrics: Manufacturers of consumer products and electronic devices can use the</p>

	<p>predictive model to assess the fatigue life of formed components in their products</p> <p>7. Research and development: Research institutions and laboratories focused on materials science and engineering can adopt the model for studying and predicting fatigue life in formed parts.</p> <p>8. Defense and military applications: Defense contractors and military organizations can apply the predictive model to estimate the fatigue life of formed components used in military vehicles, equipment, and structures.</p>
Exploitation interests	<p>CIMNE aims to make academic publications on this result and offer potential consulting services with this model to the industry.</p> <p>EUT aims at exploiting this model through licensing or commercializing it as a service, and/or keep it for internal uses.</p> <p>UPC aims to make academic publications on this result.</p> <p>LTU aims to make academic publications on this result.</p> <p>AMMR aims to keep the result for internal uses and use it to create other products.</p> <p>MW aims to keep the result for internal uses and use it to improve our processes</p>
Potential exploitation agreements	<p>1.Non-Exclusive Licensing and Service Provision Agreement: EUT, which aims to license or commercialize the model, can enter into a non-exclusive licensing agreement with CIMNE. The licensing terms can specify how UET can use and license the model for commercial purposes. It can also outline provisions for offering the model as a service. CIMNE can retain the right to provide consulting services based on the model.</p> <p>2.Academic Collaboration and Publication Agreement: UPC and LTU, which aim to make academic publications on the result, can collaborate on academic research and publications. They can enter into an agreement that outlines the terms of their academic collaboration, data sharing and publication rights.</p> <p>3. Collaboration for Product Development: AMMR and MW, which intend to use the model for internal purposes and potentially create other products, can collaborate with the other partners as well to explore the development of new products or services based on the model; the agreement can outline the responsibilities and revenue-sharing arrangements related to the creation and commercialization of the new products.</p>
IPR Strategy	Patent
IPR Strategy Rationale	The algorithm involves unique and inventive features, which makes patent protection suitable. The patent will prevent others from using the algorithm without permission. No trade secret is viable since multiple partners want to make publications.

KER #10: A manufacturing method for forming and co-curing multi-material components	
Main partner	RISE
Other partners involved	Profilglass
WP(s) involved	4
Category	Procedure
Description	Efficient manufacturing method for low cycle time for cold stamped-composite structures

Unique Value Proposition	Efficient one-step process to combine pre-impregnated composite plies to metal layers
Competitors	<p>1.Composite manufacturing technology providers: Companies specializing in composite manufacturing technologies, including methods for forming and co-curing multi-material components</p> <p>2.Advanced materials suppliers: Suppliers of advanced materials, such as composite materials and hybrid allows, that are used in the manufacturing of multi-material components.</p> <p>3.Automated manufacturing solutions providers: entities offering automated manufacturing solutions, including those with technologies for forming and co-curing multi-material components in an efficient and high-volume manner</p> <p>4. Research institutions and universities: Academic institutions engaged in research on advanced manufacturing technologies and materials, potentially developing alternative methods for multi-material component manufacturing.</p> <p>5. Material science and engineering companies: Companies with expertise in materials science and engineering, offering solutions for manufacturing components with specific material properties.</p>
Time to Market	M72
Initial TRL	TRL 2
Final TRL	TRL 5
Potential target	<p>1.Automotive industry: Manufacturers can use the method for forming and co-curing multi-material components in vehicles, enhancing structural integrity, reducing weight, and improving fuel efficiency</p> <p>2.Aerospace and aviation: Aerospace companies can apply the method to manufacture lightweight and durable multi-material components for aircraft, contributing to fuel efficiency and performance</p> <p>3.Consumer electronic: Companies producing electronic devices can leverage the method to manufacture multi-material components for lightweight and durable products</p> <p>4.Renewable energy: Manufacturers in the renewable energy sector can use the method for producing multi-material components with enhanced strength and durability.</p> <p>5.Medical devices: Medical device manufacturers can adopt the method for producing multi-material components used in devices that require a combination of strength and flexibility</p> <p>6.Construction and infrastructure: Construction companies can apply the method for forming and co-curing multi-material components in structures, providing a balance of strength and reduce weight.</p> <p>7.Defense and military applications: Defense contractors and military organizations can use the method for manufacturing multi-material components in military vehicles and equipment to achieve a balance of strength and weight reduction.</p> <p>8.Electrical and industrial equipment: companies producing electrical and industrial equipment can adopt the method for manufacturing components with specific material properties tailored to the application</p> <p>9.Research and Development institutions: Institutions focused on materials science and engineering can adopt the</p>

	method for research purposes and collaborate with industries for further innovation
Exploitation interests	RISE aims to keep the result for internal processes and potentially offer consulting services with this model to the industry. Profilglass aims at commercializing this manufacturing method.
Potential exploitation agreements	1.Licensing Agreement: RISE and Profilglass can enter into a licensing agreement that grants Profilglass the right to commercialize the manufacturing method. The licensing terms should outline how they can use the method, including exclusivity arrangement, licensing fees, and terms for sublicensing. RISE can retain the right to use the method for internal processes while offering consulting services to the industry. 2. Service Provision Agreement: RISE, which aims to offer consulting services related to the method, can establish a service provision agreement with Profilglass; this agreement can define the terms and conditions for providing consulting services, including pricing, revenue sharing, and related responsibilities.
IPR Strategy	Trade Secret/Patent
IPR Strategy rationale	Patent protection is suitable, since the method involves unique features that provide a competitive advantage. Previously it can be protected with a trade secret.

KER #11: Pre-impregnation method for fiber reinforcement	
Main partner	CSE
Other partners involved	RISE
WP(s) involved	7
Category	Procedure
Description	Implementation of high-speed manufacturing of prepreg composites
Unique Value Proposition	More effective manufacturing methods compared to other traditional methods
Competitors	1.Traditional prepreg manufacturing companies: Established companies specializing in traditional methods of prepreg manufacturing, which may include different techniques for fiber reinforcement 2.Aerospace and automotive composite suppliers: Companies providing composite materials and prepreg specifically tailored for the aerospace and automotive industries 3. Material science and engineering companies: Companies with expertise in materials science and engineering, offering solutions for fiber reinforcement and composite manufacturing 4.Research institutions and universities: Academic institutions engaged in research on advanced materials and manufacturing technologies, potentially developing alternative methods for fiber reinforcement prepregs. 5. Other composite suppliers for the potential market: Companies supplying composite materials, potentially using alternative methods for fiber reinforcement in prepregs.
Time to Market	M48
Initial TRL	3
Final TRL	5

Potential target	<p>1. Automotive industry: Automotive manufacturers can apply the method to produce prepreg composites for vehicle components, contributing to weight reduction and improved fuel efficiency</p> <p>2. Aerospace and aviation: Companies in the aerospace industry can use the pre-impregnation method for manufacturing lightweight and high-strength prepreg composites to aircraft structures.</p> <p>3. Wind energy: Manufacturers in the wind energy sector can use the pre-impregnation method for producing composite materials used in the construction of lightweight and durable wind turbine blades.</p> <p>4. Sports and recreation equipment: Companies producing sports equipment, such as bicycles, tennis rackets, and golf clubs, can adopt the method for manufacturing high-performance and lightweight composite components</p> <p>5. Marine industry: Manufacturers in the marine industry can use the pre-impregnation method for producing composite materials for boat structures, enhancing strength and reducing weight.</p> <p>6. Defense and military applications: Defense contractors and military organizations can apply the method for manufacturing lightweight and strong prepreg composites used in military vehicles and equipment.</p> <p>7. Infrastructure and construction: Construction companies can use the method for producing materials used in infrastructure projects.</p> <p>8. Industrial equipment: Companies producing industrial equipment can use the method for manufacturing prepreg composites with specific properties tailored to industrial applications</p> <p>9. Research and development institutions: Institutions focused on materials science and engineering can adopt the method for research purposes and collaborate with industries for further innovation.</p>
Exploitation interests	CSE aims to keep the result for internal processes. RISE aims to keep the result for internal processes.
Potential exploitation agreements	1. Internal Use Agreement: CSE and RISE can enter into an internal use agreement that outlines how they will individually implement and use the pre-impregnation method for their internal processes. This agreement can cover details such as data sharing, updates, and collaboration if they decide to further develop or optimize the method for their specific interests.
IPR Strategy	Trade Secret/Patent
IPR Strategy Rationale	Given the competitive nature of the composite manufacturing industry, safeguarding key manufacturing processes as trade secrets can offer a strategic advantage. In the future this could evolve into a patent.

KER #12: AHSS grades with improved fatigue resistance	
Main partner	AMMR
Other partners involved	MW, UPC
WP(s) involved	1,2,7
Category	Know How

Description	New steels with improved properties as fatigue/fracture resistance vs formability compromise, for various industrial applications.
Unique Value Proposition	Guidelines for the development of new materials
Competitors	<p>1. Steel manufacturers and suppliers: established steel manufacturers offering AHSS grades and continuously innovating to enhance fatigue resistance</p> <p>2. Materials science and engineering companies: Companies specializing in materials science and engineering, providing advanced steel allows and grades with improved fatigue resistance.</p> <p>3. Traditional supplier from the clients: Companies supplying materials, with experience in sectors where high fatigue resistance is critical for structural integrity.</p>
Time to Market	M72
Initial TRL	1
Final TRL	3
Potential target	<p>1. Automotive industry: AHSS grades with improved fatigue resistance can find extensive applications in the automotive sector for manufacturing lightweight, high-strength components that contribute to fuel efficiency and crashworthiness</p> <p>2. Aerospace and aviation: The aerospace industry can use AHSS grades with enhanced fatigue properties in the production of structural components for aircraft, providing a balance of strength and weight reduction</p> <p>3. Transportation and rail: Companies involved in the manufacturing of heavy-duty transportation vehicles and rail systems can benefit from AHSS grades that offer superior fatigue resistance for extended service life</p> <p>4. Energy and infrastructure: Applications in the energy sector, including infrastructure projects such as bridges and power transmission towers, can benefit from the use of AHSS grades with improved fatigue performance for increased durability</p> <p>5. Heavy machinery and equipment: Manufacturers of heavy machinery and equipment, such as construction machinery and agricultural equipment, can integrate AHSS grades with enhanced fatigue resistance for robust and long-lasting components</p> <p>6. Marine and offshore structures: The marine industry can use AHSS grades for constructing durable and fatigue-resistant components in ships and offshore structures subjected to dynamic loading conditions.</p> <p>7. Defense and military applications: AHSS with improved fatigue resistance can be applied in the defense sector for manufacturing military vehicles, armor, and equipment with increased durability under harsh conditions</p> <p>8. Consumer goods and appliances: Applications in consumer goods, such as sporting equipment, household appliances, and tools, where lightweight and durable materials are desirable</p> <p>9. Manufacturing and fabrication: General manufacturing and fabrication industries that require high-strength steel components for various applications, including those subject to cyclic loading.</p> <p>10. Automotive aftermarket: Suppliers in the automotive aftermarket can offer replacement components made from</p>

	AHSS grades with improved fatigue resistance, providing performance upgrades for existing vehicles.
Exploitation interests	AMMR aims to keep the result internally to create other products. MW aims to use to keep the material internally to create other products. UPC aims to make academic publications on this result.
Suggested exploitation agreements	1.Non-Exclusive Licensing Agreement for Academic Collaboration: AMMR and MW, who aim to keep the material for internal product development, can consider granting UPC a non-exclusive license to use the material for academic purposes and to collaborate on research. UPC can use the material for academic publications while respecting the licensing terms and research collaboration requirements. 2.Collaboration for Product Development: AMMR and MW, who intend to keep the material for internal use and create other products, can collaborate on the development of new products or services based on the improved AHSS grades. This agreement should outline the responsibilities and revenue-sharing arrangements related to the creation and commercialization of new products.
IPR Strategy	Patent
IPR Strategy Rationale	This protection would be recommended in this case since unique formulations and processing techniques will be present. Highlighting the specific allow compositions, heat treatment methods, or other proprietary processes that distinguish the enhanced fatigue properties is crucial.

KER #13: Al alloys grades with improved fatigue resistance	
Main partner	Profilglass
Other partners involved	UPC
WP(s) involved	1,2,7
Category	Materials
Description	New Al alloy grades with enhanced properties and performance for various industrial applications
Unique Value Proposition	
Competitors	1.Aluminium alloy manufacturers and suppliers: Established manufacturers specializing in the production of advanced aluminum alloys, offering a range of materials for various applications, including those focusing on fatigue resistance improvements. (e.g. Alcoa, Arconic, Novelis, Constellium). 2. Research institutions and universities: Institutions engaged in materials research and development, that could develop alternative formulations and processing methods.
Time to Market	
Initial TRL	
Final TRL	
Potential target	1.Aerospace and aviation: the aerospace industry can benefit from Al alloys with improved fatigue resistance for manufacturing lightweight components in aircraft, leading to fuel efficiency and increased structural integrity 2.Automotive industry: automotive manufacturers can use Al alloys to produce lightweight components with superior fatigue resistance, contributing to the overall efficiency, performance, and fuel economy of vehicles.

	<p>3. Defense and military applications: Military and defense applications can benefit from Al alloys with enhanced fatigue resistance properties for durability in challenging conditions.</p> <p>4. Energy sector: Al alloys may find applications in the energy sector, particularly in components used in power generation, transmission, and renewable energy systems, where lightweight materials with high fatigue resistance are crucial.</p> <p>5. Medical devices and implants: The medical industry can use Al alloys for manufacturing lightweight and durable components for medical devices and implants, enhancing biocompatibility and fatigue performance.</p> <p>6. Consumer electronics: Manufacturers of consumer electronics can integrate Al alloys into devices and gadgets to reduce weight and improve durability, catering to the demand for lightweight and robust materials.</p> <p>7. Sports and recreation equipment: Companies producing sports equipment, such as bicycles, golf clubs, and racquets, can explore the use of Al alloys for lightweight and high-performance products with improved fatigue resistance.</p> <p>8. Marine and offshore industry: The marine sector can benefit from Al alloys in the construction of lightweight and corrosion-resistant components for ships and offshore structures, ensuring durability in harsh marine environments.</p> <p>9. Automotive aftermarket: Suppliers in the automotive aftermarket can offer replacement components from Al alloys with improved fatigue resistance, providing performance upgrades for existing vehicles.</p> <p>10. Manufacturing and industrial equipment: Al alloys may be applied in the manufacturing of industrial equipment, machinery, and tools where the combination of lightweight properties and fatigue resistance is advantageous.</p>
Exploitation interests	<p>Profilglass has interests on commercializing this result. UPC aims to make academic publications on this result.</p>
Potential exploitation agreements	<p>1. Licensing Agreement with Academic Collaboration Component: Profilglass can enter into a licensing agreement with UPC. The agreement should specify the terms and conditions for Profilglass to use and commercialize the new aluminium alloy grades. Additionally, the agreement should include a component for academic collaboration, allowing UPC to use the alloys for academic research and publications. This combined approach allows both commercialization and academic collaboration, ensuring a structured and mutually beneficial arrangement that respects both parties' interests.</p>
IPR Strategy	Patent
IPR Strategy Rationale	Patent is recommended to protect the uniqueness of the formulations, highlighting unique compositional elements and other proprietary methods that distinguish the fatigue-resistant properties.

KER #14: New hybrid metal-composite with improved fatigue resistance	
Main partner	RISE
Other partners involved	Profilglass, CSE
WP(s) involved	1,2,7
Category	Materials

Description	New hybrid metal-composite material with enhanced properties and behavior for various industrial applications.
Unique Value Proposition	Lightweight solution with mechanical properties comparable to conventional metals
Competitors	<p>1.Composite material manufacturers: Companies specializing in composite materials may develop hybrid solutions (e.g. Hexcel)</p> <p>2.Metal matrix composite suppliers: Suppliers focusing on metal matrix composites may create hybrid materials that incorporate both metallic and composite properties (e.g. Materion)</p> <p>3.Specialized material providers: Entities supplying materials for specialized industries such as aerospace and automotive may explore hybrid materials (e.g. Toray, Continental Structural Plastics, Owens Corning, Gurit Holding, Solvay).</p>
Time to Market	3-5 years after the project
Initial TRL	MRL 3 (TRL 2)
Final TRL	MRL 5-6 (TRL 4-5)
Potential target	<p>1.Automotive industry: Applications in lightweight automotive components, such as body panels, chassis parts, and structural elements, where the hybrid material can offer a balance of strength, durability and reduced weight.</p> <p>2.Aerospace and aviation: Components for aircraft structures that require a combination of the lightweight properties of composites and the strength of metallic materials, contributing to fuel efficiency and overall performance.</p> <p>3.Marine and offshore industry: Construction of ships and offshore structures with enhanced fatigue resistance, corrosion resistance, and weight reduction compared to traditional materials.</p> <p>4.Renewable energy: Wind turbine components, such as blades and structural elements, benefitting from the lightweight characteristics and improved fatigue resistance of the hybrid material.</p> <p>5.Sports and recreation equipment: Manufacturing of sports equipment, such as bicycle frames, golf clubs, and other athletic gear</p> <p>6. Defense and military applications: Military vehicles, equipment and structures that require materials with superior fatigue resistance and durability under varying operational conditions</p> <p>7.Construction and infrastructure: use in construction elements, bridges, and infrastructure projects where the hybrid material's properties can contribute to longevity and reduced maintenance</p> <p>8.Consumer electronics: Integration with electronic devices, gadgets, and casings where the hybrid material can provide a balance between structural integrity and weight reduction.</p> <p>9. Medical devices and implants: Manufacturing of lightweight and durable components for medical devices and implants, where the hybrid material's properties could meet specific biocompatibility and fatigue requirements.</p> <p>10.Energy sector: Components used in the energy sector, including power transmission structures and equipment, benefiting from the hybrid material's fatigue resistance and reduced weight.</p>

Exploitation interests	CSE has no interests in exploiting this result. Profilglass has interests on commercializing this result.
Suggested exploitation agreements	1.Collaborative Commercialization Agreement: CSE and Profilglass can enter into a collaborative commercialization agreement to jointly exploit the result for various industrial applications. This agreement should outline the responsibilities and contributions of each party in the commercialization process, and can include provisions for sharing development costs, revenue-sharing mechanisms, and any exclusivity arrangements or territorial considerations. It should also establish clear intellectual property rights, and outline any licensing arrangements or sublicensing rights.
IPR Strategy	Trade Secret/ Patent
IPR Strategy Rationale	It is recommended to file for a patent to protect the unique formulation and composition of the material, highlighting the specific combination of its elements. Previously, a trade secret can be signed in order to enhance its protection.

KER #15: New wheel produced with high strength steel-grades	
Main partner	MW
Other partners involved	-
WP(s) involved	4,6,7
Category	Product
Description	A new wheel product that improves material possibilities for lightweight design of Electric LCV
Unique Value Proposition	A wheel with reduced weight and reduced carbon footprint
Competitors	1.Manufacturers and suppliers that produce wheels or wheel-related products, (often specialized in some sectors, such as automotive or aerospace) (e.g, Maxion Wheels, Accuride, TOPY Wheel, Steel Strip Wheel Ltd, JSWheels Jantsa, Jingu, Safran Landing Sytems, Titan International, Trelleborg Wheel Systems, Unfeverth Manufacturing Company)
Time to Market	M72
Initial TRL	4
Final TRL	6
Potential target	1.Automotive industry: Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs) and aftermarket suppliers targeting automotive applications 2.Aerospace and aviation: Manufacturers of aircraft and aerospace equipment looking for high-strength and lightweight materials for landing gear and other structural components. 3.Defense and military applications: Suppliers catering to military vehicles, armored personnel carriers, and defense applications where high-strength materials are essential. 4.Heavy machinery and construction equipment: Manufacturers of heavy-duty machinery, construction equipment, and earth-moving vehicles that require robust and durable wheels. 5.Marine and offshore industry: Shipbuilders and offshore platform manufacturers seeking high-strength wheels for marine applications 6.Mining and quarrying: Companies in the mining and quarrying sector requiring durable wheels for heavy-duty vehicles used in extraction and transportation

	<p>7.Agricultural machinery: Manufacturers of agricultural equipment</p> <p>8.Material handling and logistics: Providers of material handling equipment (forklifts, industrial trucks...)</p> <p>9.Energy sector: Suppliers to the energy sector requiring robust wheels for specialized equipment</p>
Exploitation interests	MW has interest in commercializing the new product with new grades and new methodology of the process
Potential exploitation agreements	No exploitation agreements needed as only one partner has expressed interesting in exploiting this result.
IPR Strategy	Trade secret
IPR Strategy Rationale	The most appropriate strategy is to protect the unique and specific characteristics of the process of producing the wheel, including specific features, patterns or configurations that contribute to its distinctive design, and keep it secret within MW.

KER #16: Method for structural health monitoring by embedded sensors	
Main partner	RISE
Other partners involved	-
WP(s) involved	5
Category	Procedure
Description	Integration of fiber-optical sensors in FRP hybrid material for health monitoring was demonstrate by embedded sensors when exposed to cyclic loading
Unique Value Proposition	Embedding sensors inside material when needed as compared to surface mounted sensors
Competitors	<p>1.Wireless sensor network providers: Companies specializing in wireless sensor networks for structural health monitoring, offering solutions for continuous data collection and analysis (e.g. Libelium)</p> <p>2.IoT-based structural health monitoring platforms: Providers of IoT platforms and solutions tailored for structural health monitoring applications, incorporating embedded sensors and data analytics. (e.g. Dell)</p> <p>3.Vibration monitoring systems: Companies offering vibration monitoring systems for structures (e.g. Bruel & Kjaer)</p> <p>4.Fiber optic sensing technology providers: Companies leveraging fiber optic sensing technology for structural health monitoring (e.g. Luna innovations)</p> <p>5.Ultrasonic monitoring technology: Providers of ultrasonic monitoring technologies that use ultrasonic sensors to detect changes in material properties and structural conditions (e.g. SONOTEC)</p> <p>6.Acousting emission monitoring systems: Companies specializing in acoustic emission monitoring systems for structural health, detecting acoustic signals associated with structural changes (e.g. MISTRAS Group)</p> <p>7. Structural health monitoring software providers: developers of software platforms specifically designed for structural health monitoring (e.g. Kinemetrics)</p>
Time to Market	M72
Initial TRL	TRL 3
Final TRL	TRL 4
Potential target	1.Civil engineering and infrastructure: Monitoring the health of bridges, tunnels, dams, and other critical

	<p>infrastructure to ensure public safety and optimize maintenance schedules</p> <p>2. Building construction and management: Integrating embedded sensors in commercial and residential buildings for real-time monitoring of structural health and early detection of potential issues.</p> <p>3. Transportation and railways: Monitoring the structural health of railways, train tracks, and transportation infrastructure to enhance safety and prevent accidents.</p> <p>4. Aerospace and aviation: Embedding sensors in aircraft structures to monitor and assess the health of critical components, ensuring safe and reliable air travel</p> <p>5. Automotive industry: Implementing structural health monitoring in vehicles to detect and address issues related to chassis integrity and safety.</p> <p>6. Energy sector: Monitoring the structural integrity of oil rigs, pipelines, and storage facilities to prevent environmental hazards to ensure operational safety. Also, wind turbines, solar panel structures, and other renewable energy installations for structural health to optimize performance and prevent failures.</p> <p>7. Maritime and offshore structures: Embedding sensors in ships, offshore platforms, and maritime structures to monitor the impact of environmental conditions and structural integrity</p> <p>8. Military and defense: Implementing structural health monitoring in military vehicles, equipment, and infrastructure to enhance operational safety and extend equipment lifespan</p> <p>9. Manufacturing and industrial plants: Monitoring the structural health of manufacturing facilities, production equipment, and industrial structures to prevent downtime and improve safety.</p> <p>10. Telecommunications infrastructure: Embedding sensors in cell towers and communication infrastructure to monitor structural health and optimize maintenance schedules</p> <p>11. Mining and extractive industries: Monitoring the structural integrity of mining facilities, equipment, and tunnels to ensure worker safety and prevent accidents.</p>
Exploitation interests	RISE aims to exploit the method, or parts of it, in other applications both for internal use and consultancy.
Potential exploitation agreements	No exploitation agreements needed
IPR Strategy	Patent
IPR Strategy Rationale	It is worth pursuing a patent strategy to protect the unique aspects of the embedded sensor technology and the methodology for structural health monitoring.

2.3 Aggregated Canvas Model

Let by a Consortium of diverse Partners, the project encompasses a multifaceted exploitation strategy. The exploitation activities involve multiple partners of different sectors that aim at exploiting in a diverse way each of the results. As it has been previously analyzed, making a business plan for each of the results is not feasible, as each Partner has its own goals and aims at exploiting each result in a different way. For this reason, we provide an aggregated Business Canvas Model for the project, providing a general overview of how Fatigue4Light aims to reach the market in an aggregated way. The Fatigue4Light Canvas model is presented below:

Figure 1: Fatigue4Light canvas model

For the ease of the reader, the explanation of each element of the Business Model Canvas is presented here:

1. Customer segments:

- Primary customers: Those customers that are more likely to need and acquire Fatigue4Light's exploitable results. This includes Automotive manufacturers (and its aftermarket), Aerospace companies, Energy companies, and Infrastructure developers.
- Secondary customers: Those customers that are still likely to need Fatigue4Light's exploitable results but are less prioritized due to other reasons (such as Partners' expertise, Partners' priorities, or less transferability among the different exploitable results. This includes Military and defense, Maritime and offshore infrastructure, Extractive industries and mining, and Research and Development institutions.

2. Value proposition:

- Innovation in Lightweight Solutions: Reduction in chassis weight, leading to improved EV efficiency.
- Advanced materials: Introduction of high-performance materials (AHSS, stainless steel, Al alloys...) with enhanced fatigue resistance.
- Predictive Modeling: Cutting-edge fatigue numerical models, software and methodologies for faster and more accurate fatigue prediction.
- Eco-design and sustainability: Consideration of sustainability throughout the project, including LCA assessments.

3. Channels

- Direct sales: Engaging directly with manufacturers for the adoption of lightweight solutions.
- Consulting services: Offering consulting services based on the developed models to industries.
- Publications and dissemination: Sharing findings and methodologies through academic publications, conferences, and workshops.

4. Customer relationships

- Collaborative partnerships: Establishing collaborations with industry partners for improving results and jointly exploiting them.
- Continuous engagement: Maintaining ongoing relationships with customers through feedback, updates, and support services.
- Education and awareness: Educating customers about the benefits of lightweight solutions and advanced modeling techniques.

5. Revenue streams

- Product sales: Generating revenue through the sale of innovative lightweight solutions and materials.
- Consulting services: Offering consulting services based on the developed models to industries.
- Licensing and partnerships: Exploring opportunities for licensing and partnerships with companies interested in specific results.

6. Key resources

- Research and Development team: Core team responsible for the development of innovative solutions and methodologies
- Industry partners: Collaborating with industry for real-world applications.
- IP portfolio: Protecting and leveraging intellectual property through a complete IPR strategy for sustained competitiveness.

7. Key activities

- Material development: Ongoing research and development of advanced materials with high fatigue performance
- Model validations: continuous validation of fatigue numerical models through lab scale and industry demonstrators
- Eco-design integration: Ensuring sustainability is considered in all aspects.

8. Key Partnerships

- Other project Partners: Partnerships among Fatigue4Light Partners that have commonly contributed to achieving a particular exploitable result.
- Industry collaborators: Partnerships with key industry players
- Consulting partners Collaborations with consulting firms for offering specialized services based on project outcomes.
- Research and Development institutions: Engaging with research institutions for joint projects (that could emerge from Fatigue4Light), further validation, and dissemination.

9. Cost structure

- Research and Development: Investment in R&D activities for material development, modelling, and testing
- Testing and validation: Costs associated with lab-scale and industrial demonstrators for result validation.
- Marketing and dissemination: Allocating resources for disseminating project findings, publications, and attending conferences.

2.4 Market Analysis

Introduction

In this section we present a market analysis for each of the potential primary customers for Fatigue4Light.

Analysis

Automotive manufacturers

The automotive manufacturing sector represents a dynamic and evolving industry with a focus on innovation, efficiency and sustainability, especially the electric vehicle market. The global automotive manufacturing market is valued at approximately 2.95 trillion dollars (2022)¹, with a steady growth to recover after COVID-19. It is expected a steady growth, driven by rising demand for vehicles, especially electric and hybrid models. It is projected that electric vehicles reach a demand of \$906.7 billion by 2028, with a steady annual growth rate (CAGR 2023-2028) of 10.07%², thanks to increasing investments in electric vehicles technology, environmental concerns, and government incentives.

In this landscape, automotive manufacturers are increasingly prioritizing sustainable practices and materials; lightweight solutions align with these sustainability goals, contributing to reduced energy consumption and emissions. New regulations make manufacturers seek solutions that comply with environmental standards without compromising performance.³

¹ Statista (2023) <https://www.statista.com/statistics/574151/global-automotive-industry-revenue/>

² Statista (2023) <https://www.statista.com/outlook/mmo/electric-vehicles/worldwide>

³ Allied Market Research (2022) "Electric vehicle market by type, vehicle type, vehicle class, top speed and vehicle drive type: Global opportunity analysis and industry forecast, 2021-2030

For these reasons, Fatigue4Light results can capitalize this global trend towards electric mobility, position lightweight materials at the forefront of addressing a critical need in the automotive industry.

Aerospace companies

The aerospace industry is characterized by its demand for cutting-edge material, stringent safety standards, and a continuous pursuit of innovation. The aircraft manufacturing market size was valued at \$413.51 billion in 2021 and is expected to grow at a CAGR of 3.7% until 2030⁴.

There is a critical demand for materials that significantly reduce the weight of aircraft components while doing an emphasis on maintaining or improving structural integrity and durability. For this, there is a requirement for materials with superior fatigue resistance that can withstand the cyclical stresses experienced during aircraft operation. Here is a need for tools that provide precise predictions of fatigue performance for advanced design optimization and modeling solutions that facilitate the development of lighter and more fuel-efficient aircraft. These needs are found in a context of increasing air travel, a demand for fuel-efficient aircraft to reduce operational costs and environmental impact, and a trend toward lightweight materials to achieve fuel efficiency goals.

Fatigue4Light Partners can capitalize this needs to enter an industry with an ongoing pursuit of lightweight and efficient aircraft.

Energy companies

Energy and renewable energy companies operate in dynamic markets driven by technological advancements, sustainability goals and the global transition towards cleaner energy sources. Renewable energy is a giant market that is expected to growth at a CAGR of 8.4% until 2030⁵, and its growth will be driven by the transition towards sustainable energy sources and environmental considerations. There are increasing investments to make more efficient and durable components (such as turbine components in wind energy). Fatigue4Light results can contribute to the efficiency and durability of renewable energy systems by addressing industry-specific challenges regarding the needs for new materials due to regulations and the adoption of more efficient practices.

Infrastructure developers

Infrastructure developers play a pivotal role in shaping sustainable and resilient cities, transportation networks, and buildings. Construction is a market with an anticipated growth driven by urbanization, population growth, and infrastructure development project.⁶ Companies are increasingly adopting sustainable construction practices and materials, seeking efficient structures that meet durability and environmental impact standards. Materials that could contribute to the efficiency, durability and sustainability of infrastructure projects would be welcomed.

Fatigue4Light results could have a space in mega infrastructure projects, tailoring solutions for regional requirements, and integrating the results into sustainable construction practices. For this industry is necessary reliable, efficient materials that resist fatigue, something that Fatigue4Light can provide to the industry.

⁴ Polaris Market Research (2022) “Aircraft manufacturing market share, size, trends, industry analysis report, by product; by application; by region; segment forecast, 2022-2030

⁵ Allied Market Research (2021) “Renewable energy market by type and end use: global opportunity analysis and industry forecast, 2021-2030

⁶ Statista (2019) “Global construction industry – statistics & facts”

2.5 PESTLE Analysis

In this section we develop a PESTLE analysis applied to Fatigue4Light and its exploitable results. PESTLE stands for Political, Economic, Sociocultural, Technological, Legal and Environmental, and is a tool that we will use to provide a macro picture of the environment in which Fatigue4Light has to navigate.

Political

- There's a government backing or research and development initiatives in sustainable manufacturing, through funding programs or policy incentives.
- European political stability is good enough to facilitate international collaborations.
- There could be changes in international trade relations with non-European regions that may affect the availability of certain materials.

Economic

- There could be problems with funding for research and development projects during a potential economic recessions due unforeseen circumstances related to war (Ukraine, Israel).
- Also related to this, there could be potential fluctuations in material prices and economic conditions that may affect the results' cost-effectiveness.
- There's an economic trend for increased demand for lightweight materials.

Social

- Safety and sustainability awareness: The results align with the societal shift towards safety-conscious and sustainable practices.
- In some cases, there could be skepticism towards new materials and manufacturing processes.
- A shortage of skilled professionals in advanced materials could pose challenge for the results implementation.

Technological

- There's an opportunity to leverage technological advancements to enhance predictive modeling accuracy.
- Also, Partners could explore digital twin transition, and seek for opportunities to integrate project outcomes with emerging technologies for comprehensive infrastructure design and monitoring.
- Fast-paced evolution of technology may require continuous adaption of methodologies to stay current.

Legal

- Evolving and complex regulatory requirements may pose challenges in ensuring compliance for materials and methodologies, so there's a need to stay informed about regulatory compliance.

Environmental

- The project aligns with global environmental initiatives by providing materials and methodologies that contribute to sustainable manufacturing.
- However, the sourcing of certain materials may face challenges based on their availability and scalability.

2.6 Conclusions of the exploitation plan

The Fatigue4Light project stands at the forefront of innovation, representing a collaborative effort to revolutionize the landscape of lightweight materials and fatigue resistance. The extensive research, development and experimentation undertaken by the diverse consortium of partners have yielded a multitude of exploitable results, ranging from advanced numerical models to novel manufacturing methods. However, the intricate nature of the project, with multiple Partners having varied interests on the exploitation formula of each result, renders the formulation of traditional business plans challenging.

Recognizing this complexity, the exploitation activities for Fatigue4Light have been structured to adapt to the diverse interests of the Partners. The identification of exploitable results, management of intellectual property rights, and analysis of the commercial nature of each result (and from an aggregate approach as well) are tailored to the specific nature of each outcome, with an emphasis on fostering an exploitation culture throughout the project. Furthermore, the aggregate overview provided encapsulates the collective achievements and contributions of Fatigue4Light, offering a comprehensive understanding of the commercial potential of the project.

Fatigue4Light has a huge potential to reach multiple markets. The results that have been obtained during the project are suitable not only for the EV market but also to other markets (such as the aeronautical or the energy market, among others). For this reason, we value Fatigue4Light as a project with a great market reach and the capability of transferring a great amount of generated knowledge into the industry.

3. Communication & Dissemination strategy

Eurecat, through its Research Communications Office, has taken the lead of the Fatigue4Light's dissemination and communication activities. However, it's important to note that all the partners have actively participated in these actions. The consortium has viewed communication and dissemination not only as a means of sharing Fatigue4Light outcomes but also as a strategic tool to accelerate exploitation both during and after the project's execution. This approach aims to foster awareness and facilitate the establishment of alliances with technology providers and system integrators, contributing to overall success of Fatigue4Light.

The **main objectives behind the project's communication and dissemination strategy are:**

- **To engage high-profile influential stakeholders as project supporters**, fostering market uptake and securing a critical mass of early adopters.
- **To actively promote and position the project results**, particularly in forums where valuable industrial and technological feedback can be garnered.
- **To facilitate and support the exploitation of project results and encourage market uptake.**
- **To engage key players representing indirect beneficiaries**, such as raw materials providers, components manufacturers, Electric Vehicles drivers and owners, technology suppliers, service providers.
- **To maximise the impact of the development** by providing training to the scientific and academic community, fostering further research and development.

- **To share the generated know-how** from the project with both scientific and industrial communities.
- **To establish a seamless two-way communication channel** to obtain authentic feedback on the competitiveness of the results.

It's important to highlight that, to safeguard the commercial interests of the partners, the publication of materials has been selectively executed. Exceptions are made for the submission of reports and information mandated by the contract with the Commission. In every instance, partners have made decisions regarding the delineation of project information subject to copyright or trade secrets protection and have identified components suitable for broad dissemination.

3.1 Dissemination of Fatigue4Light results

3.1.1 Participation to conferences, exhibitions, congresses and fairs

From M1 – M36, Fatigue4Light's partners have participated in **23 industrial and scientific specialised events**, including conferences, exhibitions, congresses and fairs, to publicly present the project's research done and results achieved. During the last year of the project, partners presented Fatigue4Light in **12 key events** such as the RTR Conference, eMobility World Congress, IDDRG Conference, FISITA World Congress, and others.

These actions were implemented to enhance the visibility of Fatigue4Light within both the industry and scientific communities.

Table 3: Events participated

DATE	EVENT	LOCATION	PARTNER	DESCRIPTION OF THE EVENT
8 th July 2021	International Conference on Very High Cycle Fatigue (VHCF8)	Online	POLITO	<p>Davide Salvatore Paolino and Andrea Tridello, from POLITO, presented two papers related Fatigue4Light project.</p> <p>MORE INFORMATION</p>
15 th – 17 th September 2021	International Colloquium on Mechanical Fatigue of Metals	Online	POLITO	<p>Davide Salvatore Paolino and Andrea Tridello, from POLITO, participated in the Session V organised within the Colloquium and presented the work titled "Probabilistic-S-N Curves: Likelihood Ratio Confidence Intervals and Design Curves".</p> <p>MORE INFORMATION</p>
9 th – 10 th November 2021	EARPA Form Forum	Online	EUT	<p>Fatigue4Light materials were exhibited in the Eurecat virtual booth, as a key European project boosting the use of lightweight materials in electric vehicles' chassis.</p>

				<u>MORE INFORMATION</u>
14 th – 16 th February 2022	Mediterranean Conference on Fracture and Structural Integrity (MedFract2)	Catania (Italy)	POLITO	Partners from POLITO presented the Fatigue4Light project with special emphasis in the aspects related to statistical modelling of the fatigue response. <u>MORE INFORMATION</u>
30 th May – 2 nd June 2022	International Conference "Hot Sheet Metal Forming of High-Performance Steel" (CHS2)	Barcelona (Spain)	EUT, CIMNE, LTU, GES	Partners from EUT, CIMNE, LTU and GESTAMP attended the conference. In addition, EUT and LTU presented the paper "Effect of cutting clearance and sandblasting on fatigue of thick CP800 steel sheets for heavy-duty vehicles", based on some research done within Fatigue4Light project. <u>MORE INFORMATION</u>
5 th – 9 th June, 2022	ECCOMAS Congress	Oslo (Norway)	CIMNE	Two talks based on Fatigue4Light project were presented during the congress by partners from CIMNE. <u>MORE INFORMATION</u>
16 th – 17 th June, 2022	International Conference on Advanced Materials Research (EEIGM)	Barcelona (Spain)	EUT, UPC	Sergi Parareda and Marc Mares, researchers at the Metallic and Ceramic Materials Unit of Eurecat, and Antonio Mateo from CIEFMA-UPC presented the Fatigue4Light poster, which introduces a new test developed within the project. <u>MORE INFORMATION</u>
19 th July – 23 rd June 2022	International Conference on Steels in Cars and Trucks	Milan (Italy)	MW, ArcelorMittal, EUT	Partners from MW – Gruppo CLN delivered the presentation "Fatigue life of cold formed steel wheels: an experimental study", which introduced some work done and advances achieved within the Fatigue4Light project. <u>MORE INFORMATION</u>
27 th – 1 st July 2022	European Conference on Fracture (ECF22)	Madeira (Portugal)	POLITO	Partners from POLITO delivered the presentation "Methodologies for the estimation of the LCF-VHCF

				<p>duplex P-S-N design curves”, within the framework of the session 7A “TC03 Fatigue of Engineering Materials and Structures”.</p> <p>MORE INFORMATION</p>
12 th – 14 th September 2022	Congress of Numerical Methods (CMN2022)	Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (Spain)	CIMNE	<p>Luis Antonio Gonçalves and Bàrbara Alcayde, from CIMNE, the project’s coordinator, presented two scientific talks based on Fatigue4Light investigation.</p> <p>MORE INFORMATION</p>
14 th – 17 th November 2022	TRA Conference	Lisbon (Portugal)	CIMNE, EUT	<p>Sergio Jiménez, from CIMNE, participated in the session “Improved EV efficiency, range and environmental impact through innovations in lightweight materials”, organised as part of EnLight EVs Cluster. Violeta Vargas, from EUT, attended the strategic session “LCA approaches and circular economy to enhance sustainability of mobility solutions, including tendering process”.</p> <p>MORE INFORMATION</p>
14 th – 16 th February 2023	European Conference on Results from Road Transport Research (RTR)	Brussels (Belgium)	CIMNE	<p>Sergio Jiménez from CIMNE delivered the presentation “Boosting the use of lightweight materials in Electric Vehicles’ chassis.”</p> <p>MORE INFORMATION</p>
21 st – 23 rd March 2023	eMobility World Congress	Valencia (Spain)	EUT	<p>Violeta Vargas, from Eurecat, presented the project during the session “Life Cycle Assessment for Energy Production and Storage”.</p> <p>MORE INFORMATION</p>
24 th May 2023	AQM and Strepava workshop “Innovative materials and processes for sustainable transport”	Provaglio d’Iseo (Italy)	CRF Stellantis	<p>Michele Tedesco, Global responsible for metals and anticorrosion at Stellantis CRF, presented the project delivering the presentation “Stellantis: challenges of sustainability”.</p> <p>MORE INFORMATION</p>

31 st May – 2 nd June 2023	CompTest Conference	Girona (Spain)	EUT	Project partner from Eurecat, Sergi Parareda, delivered the presentation “Assessment of mode I fatigue delamination of composites through a rapid testing method”. MORE INFORMATION
20 th – 21 st June 2023	International Munich Chassis Symposium Chassis.tech	Munich (Germany)	MW	Giorgio Gallio, from MW, presented the opportunities for steel wheels and the latest innovations developed for this purpose with a special focus on the high strength steel grades implemented through the Fatigue4Light project and hybrid wheels which include all the best features of aluminium and steel. MORE INFORMATION
19 th – 22 nd June 2023	IDDRG Conference	Luleå (Sweden)	EUT, LTU	Presenting the work titled “Fracture toughness to assess the effect of trimming on the fatigue behaviour of high-strength steels for chassis parts”, which is based on Fatigue4Light project research and some of the main results achieved. MORE INFORMATION
30 th July – 4 th August 2023	International Conference on Composites Materials (ICCM23)	Belfast (Northern Ireland)	RISE	Jocke Pettersson, project partner and senior scientist at RISE, participated in the session “Structural Health Monitoring” presenting the paper titled “Embedding Fiber Optical Sensors in FRP-Hybrid Materials”. MORE INFORMATION
3 rd – 7 th September 2023	FEMS EUROMAT	Frankfurt (Germany)	UPC	Laia Ortiz Membrado, project partner from UPC, delivered the presentation “Micromechanical and microstructural characterization of the cut edge damage of Complex-Phase and Dual-Phase steels for automotive applications”. MORE INFORMATION
5 th – 7 th September 2023	COMPLAS Conference	Barcelona (Spain)	CIMNE	Three project presentations presented during the International Conference on

				Computational Plasticity, Fundamentals and Applications. MORE INFORMATION
12 th – 14 th September 2023	COMPOSITES Conference	Trapani (Sicily, Italy)	CIMNE	Alireza Taherzadeh Fard, PhD Candidate from CIMNE, participated in the conference delivering the presentation titled “On the numerical study of debonding in laminated composites through a homogenization theory”, which introduces a new formulation for modelling delamination processes in composites done within the Fatigue4Light project. MORE INFORMATION
12 th – 15 th September 2023	FISITA World Congress	Barcelona (Spain)	UPC	Laia Ortiz Membrado, from UPC, showcased the poster titled “Micromechanical and microstructural characterization of the cut edge damage of Complex-Phase and Dual-Phase steels for automotive applications”. MORE INFORMATION
10 th October 2023	"Innovation in materials for electric mobility" Congress of the Italian Metallurgy Association	Bologna (Italy)	CRF	Michele Tedesco presented Fatigue4Light during the congress on electric mobility organised by AIM. MORE INFORMATION
5 th – 7 th February 2024	RTR Conference	Brussels (Belgium)	CIMNE	Future event confirmed, more information and agenda soon.

3.1.2 Events organisation

Since the beginning of the project partners have organised **6 events mainly focused at the scientific, academic and industrial community**. The webinars and workshops organised served to divulge and share Fatigue4Light research results.

Table 4: Project webinars and workshops organised (M1 – M36)

DATE	TITLE OF THE WEBINAR / WORKSHOP	LOCATION
18 th April 2023	EVs lightweighting assessment based on AI machine learning and numerical modelling using new materials	Online

6 th June 2023	Towards a more sustainable mobility through the implementation of advanced solutions and lightweight materials in Electric Vehicles	Online
24 th October 2023	Lightweight materials deployment in Electric Vehicles chassis parts: Fast testing methodologies	Online
28 th November 2023	Advanced Fatigue Simulation methodology for Electric Vehicles chassis parts	Online
15 th January 2024	Driving sustainability: eco-design and Life Cycle Assessment approaches for Electric Vehicles	Online
16 th January 2024	Fatigue in Automotive parts: challenges when facing lightweight construction on chassis parts	Eurecat facilities in Manresa (Spain)

Eurecat, as the main responsible of the Fatigue4Light dissemination and communication tasks, managed the registration of these events and the contacts database achieved with these webinars, as well as the preliminary promotion to increase the number of external attendants and increase the impact of the project. All the webinars were recorded, the videos published in the YouTube channel and the Fatigue4Light website and the materials shared with all the participants.

REVOLUTION & FATIGUE4LIGHT WEBINAR: “EVs lightweighting assessment based on AI machine learning and numerical modelling using new materials”

Cluster webinar organised with the REVOLUTION project to showcase and discuss about the latest innovative solutions to promote a more sustainable mobility sector and reduce the Electric Vehicles’ weight. This webinar counted with more than 50 registrants and speakers representing CIMNE, Farplas, Polytechnic University of Catalonia (UPC) and IDENER.

[MORE INFORMATION & AGENDA HERE](#)

WEBINAR

EVs lightweighting assessment based on AI machine learning and numerical modelling using new materials

April 18th | 10.00h - 12.30h CEST, Online

Fatigue4Light and REVOLUTION organized the webinar “EVs lightweighting assessment based on AI machine learning and numerical modelling using new materials” with the objective to showcase and discuss about the latest innovative solutions to promote a more sustainable mobility sector and reduce the Electric Vehicles’ weight.

The event focused on different topics from experimental to computer analysis, AI Machine Learning and numerical modelling, among others.

The webinar included presentations from experts, professionals and researchers of this field, as well as a round table to discuss about future trends and challenges.

Figure 2: View of the event information in the Fatigue4Light website including the recordings

EU Green Week Webinar “Towards a more sustainable mobility through the implementation of advanced solutions and lightweight materials in Electric Vehicles”

Webinar organised as part of the European Green Week 2023 together with the EnLight EVs cluster projects. The webinar had the objective to showcase innovative solutions that can be rapidly applied in the automotive market to reduce Electric Vehicles’ weight promoting a more resilient and sustainable mobility.

[MORE INFORMATION HERE](#)

Agenda

<p>10.00 – Welcome & Introduction Maurizio Maggiore, Senior Expert, DG Research of the European Commission</p> <p>10.10 – Lightweighting by Design: essential skills, concepts and tools for the development of lightweight and sustainable automotive components Vanessa Ventosinos, Senior Researcher, CTAG</p> <p>Pascal Lorenzini, R&D Engineer, ArcelorMittal</p> <p>Tom Lightart, Senior scientist sustainability, TNO</p> <p>10.25 – Towards a more accountable sustainable and circular mobility: The well-known eco-design and life cycle assessment pairing Violeta Vargas, advanced researcher on Environmental Impact, Eurecat</p>	<p>10.40 – Skills requirements in Industry for the introduction of New Materials enabling sustainable mobility: the example of Aluminium Nano-composites Tose Petkov, researcher, Österreichisches Gießerei-Institut (OGI)</p> <p>10.55 – Building skills for sustainable lightweight materials and digitalization techniques development in the automotive industry Andrea Dominguez Martos, R&D scientist and Project Manager, IDENER</p> <p>11.10 – Enabling the industry to shift to sustainable mobility: Methods to make lightweight automotive components a reality Clara Valero, R&D engineer, ITAINNOVA</p> <p>Guan Gong, senior scientist, RISE Research Institutes of Sweden</p> <p>11.25 – Final conclusions and Q&A</p> <p>11.45 – Closure and end of session</p>
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Figure 3: Agenda of the EU Green Week Webinar

Towards a more sustainable mobility through the implementation of advanced solutions and lightweight materials in Electric Vehicles

10.00 – 11.45 CEST | ONLINE

6th
June
2023

3-11 June 2023
#EUGreenWeek
PARTNER EVENT

Logos: ENLIGHT EVS, LEVIS (LUMEN), FATIGUE 4LIGHT, REVOLUTION, Alma, FLAMINGO

Figure 4: Social Media banners created to promote the EU Green Week webinar

Fatigue4Light Webinar “Lightweight materials deployment in Electric Vehicles chassis parts: Fast testing methodologies”

Fatigue4Light first industrial webinar organised by Eurecat with the objective to present the research and developments being carried out regarding lightweight materials deployment in

Electric Vehicles (EVs) chassis parts. The webinar, counting with more than 90 of registrants, included presentation from project partners of CIMNE, Eurecat, ArcelorMittal and MW.

[AGENDA AND INFORMATION HERE](#)

WATCH THE RECORDING

DOWNLOAD THE PRESENTATIONS

<p>The Fatigue4Light project: Boosting the use of lightweight materials in Electric Vehicles' chassis</p> <p>1 file(s) 1.38 MB</p> <p>Download</p>	<p>Understanding the fatigue behaviour of lightweight materials through a rapid fatigue test</p> <p>1 file(s) 1.18 MB</p> <p>Download</p>
<p>Self-heating tests on lightweight materials: a powerful tool for rapid fatigue estimation</p> <p>1 file(s) 1.38 MB</p> <p>Download</p>	<p>Lightweighting steel wheels: a challenge for future sustainable mobility</p> <p>1 file(s) 800.84 KB</p> <p>Download</p>

Figure 5: Recordings and materials published in the Fatigue4Light website

Fatigue4Light Webinar “Advanced Fatigue Simulation methodology for Electric Vehicles chassis parts”

CIMNE, in collaboration with Eurecat, organised the second industrial webinar of the project focused on research and developments related to the advanced fatigue simulation methodology and techniques applied within the project for Electric Vehicles chassis parts. Partners from CIMNE, Stellantis and RISE participated in the event. Almost 65 attendants participated in the webinar.

[MORE INFORMATION HERE](#)

WATCH THE RECORDING

DOWNLOAD THE PRESENTATIONS

Figure 6: Webinar information, materials and recordings included in the Fatigue4Light website

Fatigue4Light Webinar “Driving sustainability: eco-design and Life Cycle Assessment approaches for Electric Vehicles”

The last industrial webinar of Fatigue4Light aimed at showcasing the main results related to eco-design, Life Cycle Assessment methodologies and Life Cost Assessment techniques. The webinar included the participation of project partners from CIMNE and Eurecat and also the presentation of linked projects such as MARBEL, COBRA and LIBERTY. The event counted with 84 registrants.

MORE INFORMATION

Presentations

<p>Fatigue4Light H2020 project: Lightweight Evolution – An Ecodesign Methodology for Reducing Weight in Electric Vehicles and Minimizing Environmental Impact</p> <p>1 file(s) 1.37 MB</p> <p>Download</p>	<p>Analyzing the Lifecycle of Cobalt-Free Li-ion Batteries: A Sustainable Shift in Electric Vehicle Energy Sources</p> <p>1 file(s) 1.73 MB</p> <p>Download</p>
<p>Charting Sustainability in Battery Packs – A Journey through Life Cycle Assessment and Eco-Design: The case of MARBEL H2020 Project</p> <p>1 file(s) 1.17 MB</p> <p>Download</p>	<p>Correlation between circularity calculations and LCA for EV batteries. Influence of key battery life cycle parameters</p> <p>1 file(s) 747.55 KB</p> <p>Download</p>

Agenda

<p>10.00 – Welcome & Introduction</p> <p>Lucia Barbu, <i>Fatigue4Light project's coordinator and Assistant Professor</i>, CIMNE</p>	<p>10.50 – Charting Sustainability in Battery Packs – A Journey through Life Cycle Assessment and Eco-Design: The case of MARBEL H2020 Project</p> <p>José Jorge Espi, <i>Head of the Sustainable Impact Line</i>, Eurecat</p>
<p>10.05 – The Fatigue4Light project: Boosting the use of lightweight materials in Electric Vehicles' chassis</p> <p>Lucia Barbu, <i>Fatigue4Light project's coordinator and Assistant Research Professor</i>, CIMNE</p>	<p>11.05 – Correlation between circularity calculations and LCA for EV batteries. Influence of key battery life cycle parameters</p> <p>Aitor Picatoste, <i>PhD candidate and LIBERTY project partner</i>, Mondragon University</p>
<p>10.20 – Fatigue4Light H2020 project: Lightweight Evolution – An Ecodesign Methodology for Reducing Weight in Electric Vehicles and Minimizing Environmental Impact</p> <p>Violeta Vargas, <i>advanced researcher on Environmental Impact</i>, Eurecat</p>	<p>11.20 – Questions & Answers</p>
<p>10.35 – Analyzing the Lifecycle of Cobalt-Free Li-ion Batteries: A Sustainable Shift in Electric Vehicle Energy Sources</p> <p>Victor Jose Ferreira, <i>Senior researcher in LCA and LCC for energy technologies</i>, IREC</p>	<p>11.30 – Closure</p>

Figure 7: Agenda of the webinar and presentations delivered

Workshop “Fatigue in Automotive parts: challenges when facing lightweight construction on chassis parts”

Eurecat organised this physical workshop to showcase the challenges within lightweight construction for chassis parts, emphasizing fatigue testing, materials, and methodologies to optimize durability. The event presented a programme with a great array of speakers including project partners from **Eurecat, CIMNE, LTU, Gestamp, MW and UPC-CIEFMA** in collaboration with professionals and experts in the automotive sector from **SCANIA, SSAB, KTH and SEAT**.

More than 30 attendants participated physically in the event celebrated in Eurecat’s Manresa facilities promoting networking and future collaborations.

[AGENDA AND INFORMATION HERE](#)

Figure 8: Some images of the event

3.1.2.1 Organisation of the Fatigue4Light final conference

The Fatigue4Light Final Conference was organised on Friday 26th of January with the objective of publicly presenting the main results achieved within the project. The event, entitled **“The path for Electric Vehicles’ weight reduction and a zero-emissions future mobility”**, was organised online.

Experts in numerical simulation, lightweight materials deployment and sustainability approaches for the automotive sector at a European level participated in the conference that covered different topics such as computer simulation, fatigue modelling and fracture evaluation tests, fast testing methods, AHSS materials and long-life and eco-design solutions for Electric Vehicles chassis weight reduction and promote a more sustainable future mobility.

Additionally, the event featured a technical session for the presentation of different project’s topics, developments and outputs, and a round table to discuss about future perspectives for lightweight and AHSS materials and components applied to the automotive sector.

The agenda of the conference can be found here: <https://fatigue4light.eu/fatigue4light-final-conference/>

The final event of the conference was targeted to:

- Small, medium and large companies in the steel sector and automotive industry.
- Researchers in numerical simulation, characterisation, fatigue and fracture, materials recyclability, etc.
- Raw materials providers, components fabricants.
- Policy makers involved in European policies on raw materials, numerical and computer simulation, steel materials and automotive sector.

- Specialised journalists from European outlets reporting on materials, numerical simulation, AHSS, automotive innovations, etc.
- General public with interest in improving the future mobility.

During the event, project promotional materials were shared (digital flyer and factsheet), as well as all the scientific articles and publications produced during the project’s execution. On the other hand, the events’ recordings and presentations will be shared on the project website and the YouTube channel.

The Fatigue4Light Final Conference was open to all interested parties, and it was promoted through the project and partners communication channels. Additionally, private invitations and direct emails were sent to key contacts and related associations and projects. The event counted with more than **110 registrants** from across Europe.

The path for Electric Vehicles' weight reduction and a zero-emissions future mobility

Fatigue4Light project final conference

Agenda

9.15 – 10.15h
Welcome and introduction to Fatigue4Light final conference

Daniel Casellas
Scientific Director
Eurecat

Lucia Barbu
Fatigue4Light Coordinator and Head of Fatigue Unit
CIMNE

9.30h
Keynote session

Henrik Sieurin
Expert Engineer
SCANIA

10.00h
Fatigue4Light results overview

Lucia Barbu
Fatigue4Light Coordinator and Head of Fatigue Unit
CIMNE

10.15 – 10.25h
COFFEE BREAK

10.25 – 11.20h
TECHNICAL SESSION: Experimental, numerical and eco-design approaches for a sustainable automotive industry

Chair:
Lucia Barbu
Fatigue4Light Coordinator and Head of Fatigue Unit
CIMNE

10.25h
Rapid fatigue testing methodologies for lightweight design of chassis components

Sergi Parareda
Researcher at the Metallic and Ceramic Materials Unit
Eurecat

10.40h
Fatigue numerical simulation of chassis components

Sergio Jiménez
Fatigue4Light project's coordinator and Associate Lecturer
CIMNE

10.55h
Fatigue issues of formed high-strength chassis parts

Erik Olsson
Associate Professor
Luleå University of Technology

11.10h
Eco-design Methodologies for Reducing Weight in Electric Vehicles and Minimizing Environmental Impact

Violeta Vargas
Advanced researcher on Environmental Impact
Eurecat

Magdalena Juntikka
Senior researcher and project manager
RISE

11.25h
Questions & Answers

All speakers involved

11.45 – 12.55
ROUND TABLE: Future perspectives for lightweight and AHSS materials and components applied to the automotive sector

Chair:
Daniel Casellas
Scientific Director
Eurecat

Participants:

<p>Michele Maria Tedesco Global manager for Metals and Anticorrosion Stellantis CRF</p>	<p>Giorgio Gallo Research and Innovation Manager BMW (CLM Group)</p>	<p>Rémi Munier Research Engineer ArcelorMittal</p>
<p>Gustaf Gustaffson Research Engineer Gestamp Hardtech</p>	<p>Erik Marklund Senior Researcher RISE</p>	

12.55 – 13.00h
FINAL CONCLUSIONS AND CLOSURE

Daniel Casellas
Scientific Director
Eurecat

Lucia Barbu
Fatigue4Light Coordinator and Head of Fatigue Unit
CIMNE

Figure 9: Fatigue4Light final conference agenda

Speakers

Daniel Casellas

Scientific Director
Eurecat

PhD in Materials Science. Since 2000 he is working in R&D and technology transfer from research institutes to industry. He is currently the Scientific Director of Eurecat and holds an Adjunct Professor position at the Solid Mechanics Division at Luleå University of Technology (Sweden). Dr Casellas has managed applied R&D projects on different sectors, mainly in the automotive and steelmaking, but also in renewable energies and mining, among others.

In the last years he has been the scientific responsible of more than 60 funded R&D projects and industrial R&D contracts. He is the author and co-author of 81 publications in indexed scientific journals, has more than 200 contributions to international conferences and holds 3 patents, related to EWF and rapid fatigue testing. Dr. Casellas is member of the Organizing Committee of the International Conference on hot sheet metal forming of high-performance steel (CHS2, www.chs2.eu) and member of the editorial board of the journal Materials.

Lucia Barbu

Fatigue4Light Coordinator
and Head of Fatigue Unit
CIMNE

Lucia Barbu is an Assistant Professor at the Polytechnic University of Catalonia (UPC) and an Assistant Research Professor at the International Center for Numerical Methods in Engineering (CIMNE) in Spain, where she conducts her research.

Her field of speciality is the constitutive modelling of nonlinear failure processes, both under monotonic and cyclic loads, with 14 years of research experience. At CIMNE she is leading the Fatigue Research Unit and directing several PhD theses.

Henrik Sieurin

Expert Engineer
Scania CV AB

Henrik has a PhD in Materials Science from the Royal Institute of Technology (KTH) in Stockholm. For the last 10 years he has been at Scania Materials Technology, working with structural steel for trucks and buses. He has previously been working with steel related issues such as failure analyses, corrosion, mechanical testing and welding for the off shore and energy industry.

Sergi Parareda

Researcher at the Metallic and Ceramic
Materials Unit
Eurecat

Researcher in the mechanical behaviour research line of the metallic and ceramic materials unit at Eurecat. PhD in materials science and engineering, involved since 2015 in research projects focused on fatigue and fracture of metallic alloys.

Sergio Jiménez

Fatigue4Light project's coordinator
and Associate Lecturer
CIMNE

Civil Engineer and coordinator of the Fatigue4Light European H2020 project. He is developing his career as researcher at CIMNE and working as Associate Lecturer in Structural Analysis and Mechanics at UPC in Barcelona. He has combined his PhD studies in Structural Analysis developing numerical models for the study of the fatigue phenomenon with his incipient career as researcher collaborating in national and international R+D projects in the analysis of mechanical nonlinearities of metals and composite materials.

Erik Olsson

Associate Professor
Luleå University of Technology

Associate professor in Solid Mechanics at LTU Luleå University of Technology since 2021. One of his main research areas is how the material processing history affects the fatigue performance of the final component.

Violeta Vargas

Advanced researcher at the Waste,
Energy and Environmental Impact Unit
Eurecat

Violeta Vargas holds a Bachelor's in Industrial Engineering from the University of Sonora, a Master's in Natural Resources Engineering from UPC, and a Ph.D. in Environmental Sciences and Technology from the Autonomous University of Barcelona.

Her research focuses on the environmental, economic and social impacts. With expertise in Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodology, she began as an Associate Lecturer at UPC in 2016, teaching LCA to Civil and Environmental Engineering Master's students. Currently an Advanced Researcher at Eurecat, she contributes to projects like MARBEL, COBRA, Fatigue4Light, and ZEVRA, aiming to enhance the sustainability of the transition to electrified mobility.

Magdalena Juntikka

Senior researcher and project manager
RISE

She has been involved with the development of composite materials for over 15 years. Specializing in environmental sustainability, starting with a PhD on recycling of polymer composites material. She has conducted a significant number of industrial research projects on environmental sustainability, including material selection, LCA, recycling and Eco-design. Combining this knowledge with the ability to manage complex R&D projects, results in demonstrable competence and experience to analyse, evaluate and understand the environmental impact of innovative material solutions.

Rémi Munier

Research Engineer
ArcelorMittal

PhD in Mechanics of Materials (Université de Bretagne Occidentale, France, 2012). He has experience in the characterization of fatigue properties of steels (Low Cycle Fatigue, High Cycle Fatigue including fast fatigue characterization from self-heating measurements, and crack propagation). He is currently research engineer at ArcelorMittal Maizières R&D since 2018. He is working in the field of Fatigue in the team dedicated to Fatigue, Crash and Fracture of the steels developed by ArcelorMittal.

Michele Maria Tedesco

Global manager for Metals
and Anticorrosion
Stellantis CRF

Global responsible for Metals & Anticorrosion in Stellantis. Study of mechanical engineer at Politecnico di Torino. Michele is started his career in Centro Ricerche Fiat (CRF) in 2013 as sheet metal specialist, focusing his activities on steel sheets validation, mechanical characterization to support CAE simulations. In 2016 become the responsible of Sheet, tube & extruded profiles competence center. In 2019 became the responsible of Italy Metals manager. In 2022 became the global responsible of Metals for Stellantis. Advisor OEM board member of Automotive Circle and International Automotive Body Congress. Coordinator of several Stellantis projects and CRF reference for international research projects, author of numerous publications and some patents.

Giorgio Gallio

Research and Innovation Manager
MW (CLN Group)

PhD in material engineering in 2014. He is involved in automotive wheels innovation since 2014, contributing with 9 patents on new wheel products and processes. Since 2021 he became head of the research department managing international research projects in collaboration with private and public entities.

Gustaf Gustafsson

Research Engineer
Gestamp HardTech

Research Engineer at Gestamp HardTech. PhD in Solid Mechanics 2012 at Luleå University of Technology. He has been working at Gestamp HardTech for 4 years. Before that he has been working as a senior lecturer and associate professor at Solid Mechanics at Luleå University after his PhD.

Erik Marklund

Senior Researcher
RISE

Senior researcher in the Materials & Production division at RISE. PhD in polymeric composite materials from Luleå University of Technology in Sweden 2007. Erik is working in the composite technology unit in Mölndal and has 15 years' experience in composites development and material modelling at Swerea & RISE. Main areas are polymer materials, material modelling and composite mechanics.

Figure 10: Speakers of the Fatigue4Light

Figure 11: Some screenshots of the final event

3.1.3 Clustering activities

Throughout all the Fatigue4Light project execution, project partners have been in contact with researchers and members of other related projects, relevant industry associations and European institutions related to the project's fields.

The collaboration between Fatigue4Light and other groups has been fostered through the participation in pertinent events or working groups organised or attended by the institutions listed in the section **3.5.6.3. of the D10.4 Interim plan of Use and Dissemination of Results (PUDR)**.

Moreover, partners have actively interacted with other project representatives, with resulted in the constitution of the EnLightEVs Cluster, created in collaboration with the Horizon Results Booster platform.

3.1.3.1 EnLight EVs cluster

The European cluster “**EnLight EVs**” was created in 2022 to expand the impact beyond the project level. The cluster is formed by Fatigue4Light together with **REVOLUTION, FLAMINGo, LEVIS and ALMA**, EU projects funded under the same programme and topic.

The cluster, created in collaboration with the Horizon Results Booster organisation, brings together EU-funded R&D projects which are developing innovative solutions, tested in industrial pilots, that can be rapidly applied in the automotive market to reduce EVs weight, while considering structural integrity, passengers’ safety, and sustainability, through eco-design and circular practices.

Since its creation, cluster projects have performed together the following actions:

Table 5: EnLight EVs cluster activities

EnLight EVs cluster actions	
June 2022	Creation and publication of a specific page within the Fatigue4Light website compiling information about the cluster and each of its projects (https://fatigue4light.eu/enlight-evs-cluster/)
September 2022	Design and production of the EnLight EVs cluster factsheet (https://fatigue4light.eu/download/enlight-evs-european-cluster-factsheet/)
November 2022	Organisation of the special session “Improved EV efficiency, range and environmental impact through innovations in lightweight materials”, within the TRA Conference taking place in Lisbon (Portugal). MORE INFORMATION
December 2022	Production of the EnLight EVs cluster video (https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9TLCFoyUd4o&t=6s)
February 2023	Participation in the webinar “Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and its application to the automotive sector” organised by FLAMINGo and ALMA. MORE INFORMATION
February 2023	Presentation of Fatigue4Light during the special session “GV – Advanced light materials and their production processes”, organised by the cluster within the RTR Conference celebrated in Brussels (Belgium). MORE INFORMATION
April 2023	Organisation of the webinar “EVs lightweighting assessment based on AI machine learning and numerical modelling using new materials” in collaboration with the REVOLUTION project.
June 2023	As part of the EU Green Week the cluster organised a webinar titled “Towards a more sustainable mobility through the implementation of advanced solutions and lightweight materials in Electric Vehicles”
November 2023	Collaborative blog post including some EnLight EVs project’s updates published in the ALMA project website (https://almaproject.eu/enlight-evs-cluster-project-updates-2023/)
Throughout 2022 - 2023	Organisation of internal meetings with representatives from each project to plan future collaborative dissemination actions
Throughout 2022 - 2023	Social Media linkage between projects

3.1.3.2 Clustering with other projects

Fatigue4Light has also established synergies and links with other European projects, including SALIENT project, FLEXCRASH project and ToughSteel project among others.

Table 6: Clustering actions with other linked projects

Date	Project	Description of the activity
April 19 th , 2023	ToughSteel project	Michele Tedesco, Global responsible for metals and anticorrosion at Stellantis CRF, presented Fatigue4Light during the industrial workshop “Fracture toughness: an additional parameter to control sheet metal quality”, organised by the ToughSteel project on April 19 th in Ravenna (Italy). READ MORE
June 29 th , 2023	Toughsteel, MiPre and CRYSTAL projects	Sergi Parareda, project partner and researcher at Eurecat, participated in the joint industrial workshop “Advanced material characterization methods to face new challenges in the sheet steel sector”, organised by ToughSteel, CRYSTAL and MiPre, three research projects funded under the frame of the Research Fund for Coal and Steel (RFCS) programme. The workshop, celebrated last 29 th of June, took place in Eurecat’s facilities located in Manresa (Barcelona, Spain). READ MORE
September 30 th , 2023	FLEXCRASH project	Inclusion of a Fatigue4Light webinar information in the first newsletter of the FLEXCRASH project. READ MORE
October 6 th , 2023	SALEMA project	Project partners from CIMNE, the Fatigue4Light coordinator, participated in the webinar “The Circular Metal for Future Mobility: aluminium for lightweight and sustainability”, organised by the SALEMA project on Friday 6 th of October, 2023. READ MORE
January 15 th , 2024	MARBEL, LIBERTY and COBRA	Inclusion of EU-funded projects MARBEL, LIBERTY and COBRA in the Fatigue4Light webinar “Driving sustainability: eco-design and Life Cycle Assessment approaches for Electric Vehicles” READ MORE

3.1.4 Training activities

Fatigue4Light partners have advanced beyond the state-of-the-art of innovative computer simulation methods, fatigue modelling and fast testing, lightweight materials development, eco-design approaches and Life Cycle Assessment methodologies to better estimate the fatigue life of chassis components and to select the optimal materials for lighter vehicle chassis, among others.

Project events attended and organised (detailed in sections 3.1.1 and 3.1.2) were highly attended by the academic community, and, therefore, can be considered as part of the Fatigue4Light training activities. The created content aimed to share the knowledge gained throughout the project with companies, research centres, and European SMEs or mid-caps operating in the project's domains. In addition, it sought to spread the project outcomes to the scientific, educational, and business communities, laying the groundwork for future use.

On the other hand, more specifically, Lucia Barbu, the Fatigue4Light's coordinator from CIMNE, participated in three training events organised by different organisations, universities, research centres and institutions with the objective to present the project.

Table 7: Training activities

Date	Title of the action	Description
July 2021	Cycle of talks for Premis Extraordinaris de Batxillerat (Catalan Association of Research Entities)	<p>Lucia Barbu gave the talk "Computational Mechanics as a transversal tool for the industry" where the Fatigue4Light project was presented as an application example. The talk was organized by the Catalan Association of Research Entities (Associació Catalana d'Entitats de Recerca - ACER) in the cycle of talks for Premis Extraordinaris de Batxillerat and was held in online format.</p> <p>The Premis Extraordinaris de Batxillerat, awarded by the Department of Education, is a recognition of the excellence and merits of the young people who have obtained the best marks in Catalonia. The audience was formed by awarded High-School graduates that were embarking on a University path in the following year.</p>
September 2021	16 th Short Course on Computational Plasticity	Lucia Barbu presented the project in the 16 th Short Course On Computational Plasticity, held under the umbrella of the COMPLAS 2021 Conference. The talk was titled <i>Plastic damage approach to fatigue analysis</i> , and was given in person in Barcelona, Spain to an audience of approximately 35 international PhD students.
April 2022	Severo Ochoa Seminar organised by CIMNE "Numerical framework for fatigue simulation"	Presentation delivered by Lucia Barbu introducing the main developments of the Fatigue4Light project in a Severo Ochoa Seminar

		<p>organized by CIMNE and held online. The audience for the Severo Ochoa Seminars is formed by an eclectic mix of both young PhD researchers and experienced senior researchers. The average attendance for a Severo Ochoa Seminar is of 40 assistants.</p>
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Figure 12: Some images of the training activities

In a future, and whenever possible, the Fatigue4Light main results and outputs can be included as part of undergraduate and Masters programmes, as well as in PhD programmes of CIMNE, LTU, POLITO and UPC. Moreover, research results can be integrated as part of the know-how of the main research centres involved in the project such as EUT and RISE with the objective to be later shared and transferred to the industrial networks.

3.1.5 Fatigue4Light publications

The findings and progress of the Fatigue4Light collaboration have been disseminated through scientific journals, conference proceedings, and book chapters by the project partners, as well as in technical blog posts or articles in specialised media outlets.

Before any publication of Fatigue4Light results, project partners have contacted the project coordinator, the dissemination leader and IPR Manager to not infringer IP rights. Moreover, before submitting any paper or article for publication, partners informed the consortium to facilitate the check and validation of the text to be presented publicly.

3.1.5.1 Scientific publications

The Fatigue4Light research has yielded a total of **15 scientific publications** spanning from M1 to M36. These include 12 articles published in journals and 3 articles featured in conference or workshop proceedings. Additionally, 3 more publications are in production and will be submitted in some months.

To promote long-term preservation and accessibility, partners have prioritized Open Access, making articles available through gold or green open access avenues. In alignment with this objective, Eurecat created a [Fatigue4Light Zenodo Community](#) that serves as a consolidated repository for all the project-related open access publications.

As said, open access publications have been shared in the project Zenodo Account and also in the Fatigue4Light scientific production webpage section (<https://fatigue4light.eu/scientific-production/>).

Table 8: List of Fatigue4Light-related publications (M1 – M36)

TYPE	TITLE	AUTHORS	JOURNAL or CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS	DOI	STATUS
Article in Journal	Fatigue resistance evaluation of high Mn-TWIP steel through damage mechanics: a new method based on stiffness evolution	by S. Parareda; A. Lara (EUT); D. Casellas (EUT, LTU); A. Mateo (UPC).	International Journal of Fatigue (2021)	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfatigue.2021.106643	PUBLISHED
Article in Journal	Statistical models for estimating the fatigue life, the stress-life relation, and the P-S-N curves of metallic materials in Very High Cycle Fatigue: A review	by A. Tridello; C. Boursier Niutta; M. Rossetto; D.S. Paolino (POLITO) F. Berto (NTNU).	Fatigue & Fracture of Engineering Materials & Structures (2021)	https://doi.org/10.1111/ffe.13610	PUBLISHED
Article in Journal	Size-effect in Very High Cycle Fatigue: A review	by A. Tridello; C. Boursier Niutta; D.S. Paolino (POLITO) F. Berto (NTNU).	International Journal of Fatigue	NA	SUBMITTED (EMBARGOED)
Proceedings of a conference	Effect of cutting clearance and sandblasting on fatigue of thick CP800 steel sheets for heavy-duty vehicles	LTU, EUT	Proceedings of Metal Forming of High-Performance Steel (CHS2) Conference	https://zenodo.org/record/6783338#ySkX8nZBxPY	PUBLISHED (Closed Access)
Article in Journal	Design against fatigue failures: lower bound P-S-N	by A. Tridello; C. Boursier Niutta; D.S. Paolino (POLITO) F.	International Journal of Fatigue	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfatigue	SUBMITTED (EMBARGOED)

	curves estimation and influence of runout data	Berto (NTNU); M.M. Tedesco; S. Plano; D. Gabellone (CRF)		que.2022.106934	
Proceedings of a conference	Fatigue life of cold formed steel wheels: an experimental study	MW	Proceedings of the Conference on Steels in Cars and Trucks (SCT2022)	NA	SUBMITTED (Not published yet)
Article in Journal	A unified non-linear energy dissipation-based plastic-damage model for cycling loading	CIMNE, UPC	CMAME - Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering: 400 (2022)	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cma.2022.115543	PUBLISHED
Article in Journal	Comparison between Fractal and Statistical Approaches to Model Size Effects in VHCF	POLITO	Metals Journal, Special Issue "New Trends in Fatigue of Metals"	https://doi.org/10.3390/met12091499 https://doi.org/10.3390/met12091499	PUBLISHED
Article in Journal	Numerical simulation of a rapid fatigue test of high Mn-TWIP steel via a high cycle fatigue constitutive law	CIMNE, EUT	International Journal of Fatigue, Volume 168 (2023)	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfatigue.2022.107444	PUBLISHED
Article in Journal	A damage-based uniaxial fatigue life prediction method for metallic materials	UPC-CIEFMA, LTU, EUT	Materials & Design, Volume 231 (2023)	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2023.112056	PUBLISHED
Article in Journal	A rule of mixtures approach for delamination damage analysis in composite materials	CIMNE	Composites Science and Technology, Volume 242 (2023)	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2023.110160	PUBLISHED
Proceedings of a Conference	Embedding Fiber Optical Sensors in FRP-Hybrid Materials	RISE	Proceedings of the International Conference on Composite Materials (ICCM2023)	https://zenodo.org/records/8276443	PUBLISHED
Article in Journal	Simulation of metal punching and trimming using	LTU, EUT, UPC-CIEFMA	Journal of Materials Processing Tech, 321 (2023)	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmptotec.2023.10160	PUBLISHED

	minimal experimental characterization			<u>023.118148</u>	
Article in Journal	High cycle fatigue life estimation of punched and trimmed specimens considering residual stresses and surface roughness	LTU, ArcelorMittal, EUT, UPC-CIEFMA	International Journal of Fatigue (2024)	NA	To be submitted / In design
Article in Journal	Virtual fatigue testing at automotive component-level via a high cycle fatigue constitutive framework: application to a light-duty vehicle lower control arm	CIMNE, CRF	Engineering Structures	Not yet	Submitted January 2024
Article in Journal	Fatigue behaviour of Glass-Fibre-Reinforced Polymers: Numerical and Experimental Characterisation	CIMNE, RISE	Composite Structures	Not yet	Submitted November 2023
Article in Journal	Hybrid Manufacturing of a 3D-Shaped Fiber Metal Laminate	RISE	Journal of Materials Processing Technology	NA	Submitted January 2024
Article in Journal	Structural Analysis and Modelling of GFRP and FML under Fatigue Loading Conditions	RISE	International Journal of Fatigue	NA	Submitted January 2024
Article in Journal	Life Cycle Assessment of lightweight demonstrators in EV's	EUT, RISE	The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment	NA	To be submitted / In design

3.1.5.2 Specialised media articles

During the project, partners have produced some press releases targeting non-specialised stakeholders on the expected impacts and results of the Fatigue4Light project. The consortium has produced a total of **5 press releases**.

These press releases have been actively disseminated through the project's Social Media channels achieving a relevant impact on print and online media outlets. Press releases produced include:

- **February 2021** (EUT, English and translated into Spanish and Catalan) - [Eurecat involved in €5.5 million project to lighten electric vehicle chassis weight](#)
- **February 2021** (POLITO, Italian) - [Ridurre il peso dei veicoli: al via il progetto Fatigue4Light](#)
- **March 2021** (Consortium press release, in English) - [Fatigue4Light project to develop new tests and computer simulation methodologies](#)
- **January 2024** (CIMNE in collaboration with EUT, adapted and translated into Catalan and Spanish) – [CIMNE experts reduce weight of chassis components of Electric Vehicles by 40%](#)
- **January 2024** (EUT in collaboration with CIMNE, in Spanish and Catalan) - [Consiguen reducir un 40 por ciento el peso de componentes del chasis de vehículos eléctricos](#)

As a result of this activity and press releases production, Fatigue4Light was featured in a total of **7 specialised media outlets**, as listed below. It's important to mention that a final press release was produced and sent last 29th of January, so it is expected to achieve more impacts in specialised media, and also, in general media outlets at local and national level.

Table 9: Articles featuring Fatigue4Light in specialised media outlets

DATE	MEDIA	TITLE	TPOLOGY	LINK
30/01/2024	Auto Revista	Investigadores consiguen reducir el peso de los vehículos eléctricos el 40%	Online	<u>Link</u>
30/01/2024	SETRAM – Automotive Logistics	Proyecto europeo reduce un 40% el peso de los vehículos eléctricos	Online	<u>Link</u>
20/11/2023	Direct Industry E-Magazine	The New Aluminium Recycling Technology That Can Boost Europe's EV Industry	Online	<u>Link</u>
03/05/2023	Interempresas - Deformación metálica y chapa	Nuevas metodologías avanzadas de ensayo para el óptimo diseño y aplicación de materiales metálicos de alto rendimiento	Online	<u>Link</u>
13/04/2023	Vehicle Dynamics International	Eurecat joins Fatigue4Light project to reduce EV chassis weight	Online	<u>Link</u>
16/09/2021	Automotive Manufacturing Solutions	Stress test: new modelling approach for component fatigue testing	Online	<u>Link</u>
01/05/2021	Interempresas – Automoción	Eurecat participa en un proyecto para reducir el peso del chasis de vehículos eléctricos	Print	<u>Link</u>
01/04/2021	La Tribuna de Automoción	Eurecat se incorpora al proyecto Fatigue4Light	Print	<u>Link</u>

Of these articles published in specialised outlets, one was authored by partners from Eurecat and another one was a result of an interview with the Fatigue4Light coordinator.

- **May 2023** | *Nuevas metodologías avanzadas de ensayo para el óptimo diseño y aplicación de materiales metálicos de alto rendimiento*
 - o Author: Dr. Sergi Parareda, project partner and researcher at the Metallic Materials Unit of Eurecat.
 - o Outlet / Magazine: Interempresas – Deformación Metálica y Chapa
- **September 2021** | *Stress test: new modelling approach for component fatigue testing*
 - o Author: Interview with Dr. Lucia Barbu, Fatigue4Light coordinator from CIMNE.
 - o Outlet / Magazine: Automotive Manufacturing Solutions

It's worth to mention that other articles may be published in specialised media outlets in the following two-three months due to partners efforts in disseminating the results achieved during the last month of the project.

In accordance with the clipping tool, a total of **23 media impacts** (including specialised and non-specialised outlets) have been achieved, accounting for a **total audience of more than 30M**, which translates on an **Economic Value of 20K€** (value equivalent to the press impact achieved). A complete list of the media articles is shown in Annex 4.2.

3.1.5.3 Popularised publications

Apart from appearing in scientific peer-reviewed publications, press releases and specialised media impacts, Fatigue4Light partners have also disseminated the project news and achievements with popularised publications such as blog posts or articles published on Fatigue4Light website and also partners' corporate websites.

From M1 – M36, **6 articles have been published in the “Project news” section of Fatigue4Light website** (<https://fatigue4light.eu/projectnews/>), including articles on demonstrators developments, cluster creation, standardisation news and the description of some project activities and milestones.

On the other hand, Fatigue4Light partners published articles on project activities in their corporate and professional websites. Some of these publications are listed below:

- **EUT:** <https://eurecat.org/en/portfolio-items/fatigue4light/>
- **CIMNE:** <https://www.cimne.com/sqp/rtd/Project.aspx?id=889>
- **POLITO:** [https://www.dimeas.polito.it/en/news/\(idnews\)/16647](https://www.dimeas.polito.it/en/news/(idnews)/16647)
- **UPC:** <https://cit.upc.edu/en/portfolio-item/new-tests-and-computer-simulation-methodologies-for-electric-vehicle-chassis-weight-reduction/>
- **MW:** <https://www.gruppocln.com/en/news/mw-and-fatigue4light-project-0>
- **RISE:** <https://www.ri.se/en/what-we-do/projects/fatigue-modelling-and-fast-testing-of-lightweight-materials>
- **LTU:** <https://www.ltu.se/research/subjects/Halfasthetslara/Forskningsprojekt/Fatigue4Light-Forskningsprojekt-med-fokus-pa-lattvikt-och-utmattning-hos-chassikomponenter?l=en>
- **UNE:** <https://revista.une.org/33/inkplant-inn-pessme-biomat-y-fatigue4light.html>

3.1.6 Direct dissemination

3.1.6.1 Community of interest

As defined in the D10.4 Interim plan of Use & Dissemination of Results (PUDR), Eurecat created the project's Community of Interest with the objective to establish direct dissemination through direct mailing and increase the impact of our communication and dissemination activities.

The Community of Interest has been used to share information about the different webinars, workshops and other events organised within the Fatigue4Light. At M36 the list achieved with the Community of Interest sign-up form includes a total of **275 contacts**.

For more information please, refer to D10.4 Interim plan of Use & Dissemination of Results (PUDR).

3.1.6.2 One-to-one meetings

One-to-one dissemination with automotive and Electric Vehicles companies and SMEs has been executed during the last two years of the project (2022 – 2023). These actions involved various dissemination strategies such as one-to-one meetings, events organisation or information exchange via email.

Fatigue4Light partners successfully contacted and engaged with almost **30 companies and regional and national innovation agencies, associations, universities, research centres and clusters in the automotive industry**.

A bidirectional communication has been established with them, and additionally, project materials and events information have been shared with these entities to spread to their contacts. In some cases, a power point with a general presentation an overview of Fatigue4Light was presented and shared.

Table 10: List of companies, institutions and associations reached for direct dissemination

Name of the company	Type	Partner responsible
Advanced Materials Cluster – MAV	Cluster	EUT
Automotive Circle	Innovation and consultancy agency	CRF
Bax & Company	Innovation and consultancy agency	EUT, CIMNE
CIAC – Clúster de la Indústria d'Automoció de Catalunya	Cluster	EUT
CTAG – Automotive Technology Centre of Galicia	Association	EUT, CIMNE
EARPA – European Automotive Research Partners Association	Association	EUT
ELCA - European Lightweight Alliance	Cluster	EUT, CIMNE
ERTRAC - European Road Transport Research Advisory Council	Association	CIMNE
Farplas Automotive	Large company	CIMNE, EUT
Fraunhofer LBF	Research centre / university	CIMNE
GEDIA España	Large company	EUT
Gestamp España	Large company	EUT, GES
IDENER	Association	EUT, CIMNE
International Magnesium Association	Association	CIMNE
International Solid Waste Association – ISWA	Association	EUT, CIMNE
ITAINNOVA – Instituto Tecnológico de Aragón	Research centre / university	EUT, CIMNE

<u>KTH - Royal Institute of Technology</u>	Research centre / university	LTU
<u>Magnetto Automotive</u>	Large company	CRF
<u>Marelli</u>	Large company	CRF
<u>Maxion Wheels Spain</u>	Large company	EUT
<u>Meleghy Automotive Barcelona</u>	Large company	EUT
<u>Neklar Group</u>	Large company	EUT
<u>QEV TECH</u>	Large company	EUT
<u>Scania</u>	Large company	LTU
<u>SEAT</u>	Large company	EUT
<u>SSAB</u>	Large company	LTU
<u>Stellantis</u>	Large company	CRF
<u>Streparava</u>	Large company	CRF
<u>Tiberina Group</u>	Large company	CRF
<u>UNESID - Unión de Empresas Siderúrgicas</u>	Association	EUT
<u>2Zero emission</u>	Association	EUT

3.2 Fatigue4Light communication materials

As detailed in **D10.1 Project Launch and Communication and Dissemination Plan**, a wide range of channels and actions were prepared and implemented for Fatigue4Light. Throughout all the project's execution period, Eurecat as the leader of communication and dissemination, has been focused in updating these communication materials aligning them with Fatigue4Light updates and activities.

3.2.1 Corporate Visual Identity (CVI)

Fatigue4Light has maintained the same branding elements that have been implemented by Eurecat across various channels and materials. This approach ensures a consistent and easily recognizable brand identity for the Fatigue4Light project. Additionally, partners have adhered to the Corporate Visual Identity (CVI) manual throughout the project, incorporating this identity into their respective activities. For additional details, please refer to **D10.1 Project Launch and Communication and Dissemination Plan**.

3.2.2 Project website

The Fatigue4Light website (www.fatigue4light.eu), launched in February 2021, has been maintained and updated until the end of the project (M36). The public website of the project has served as the anchor for all communication and dissemination efforts, featuring fundamental project details such as objectives and benefits. It serves as a comprehensive platform showcasing dissemination activities and project outcomes. Additionally, the website functions as the primary access point for various public materials, encompassing results, deliverables, scientific publications, and more. This central hub plays a pivotal role in presenting and organizing the wealth of information related to the project.

Since its release the website has been regularly updated with news, project materials, events, etc.

Figure 13: Website structure at M3 (website launch)

Figure 14: Website structure at M36 – end of the project

The Fatigue4Light website will remain operational for a duration of 3 years post-project completion. The key performance indicators (KPIs) for the main website performance from M1 to M48 are outlined in the KPIs table in Anex 4.1, specifically under Communication KPIs. To delve deeper into the website's impact and its various sections, detailed insights are provided in the following paragraphs.

The website is equipped with **Matomo, installed in the platform's backend**, enabling comprehensive monitoring of all traffic. Monthly reports on the site's performance are generated, offering valuable insights into user engagement, traffic patterns, and other relevant metrics. This

analytical approach ensures an ongoing assessment of the website's effectiveness and allows for informed decision-making to optimize its performance and user experience throughout the extended 3-year post-project period.

Top 5 visited sites: the Fatigue4Light website has experienced visits beyond its homepage. Pages with more traffic include information about the project and its consortium and two pages with more dynamic content like the project's news section and the dissemination events.

Table 11: Web pages with more traffic. Data retrieved on January 29, 2024

	Top Web pages	Page views
1	Homepage: https://fatigue4light.eu/	3,332
2	About Fatigue4Light: https://fatigue4light.eu/about-fatigue4light/	615
3	Partners: https://fatigue4light.eu/partners/	593
4	Events participated: https://fatigue4light.eu/events-participated/	366
5	Project news: https://fatigue4light.eu/projectnews/	349

Source traffic: the majority of the traffic primarily originates from “Direct entry”, indicating users typing the Fatigue4Light website's URL directly. Subsequently, users arrive at the website through social networks, search engines (using relevant keywords), as well as via links embedded in other websites, social media publications and/or newsletters campaigns.

CHANNEL TYPE	▼ VISITS	ACTIONS
Direct Entry	2,749	10,220
⊕ Social Networks	591	1,143
⊕ Search Engines	457	1,283
⊕ Websites	139	504

Figure 15: Fatigue4Light website traffic source. Analytics retrieved on January 29th, 2024

Geographical and device traffic distribution: in terms of geographical and device traffic distribution, the majority of visits are from Spain, followed by Italy and Sweden (showcasing the partners efforts in disseminating the project in their own countries). The picture is also significant to see that the project's has impacted beyond European borders. Regarding devices, most of the sessions have been established through desktop devices.

COUNTRY	VISITS
Spain	2,415
Italy	248
Sweden	212
United States	175
Germany	141
France	116
Turkey	70
United Kingdom	70
Netherlands	53

Visitor Map

Figure 16: Visitors' country of origin

TYPE	VISITS
Desktop	3,084
Smartphone	768
Phablet	31
Tablet	7

Figure 17: Device category assessing the website

In July 2020, a new directive from the Spanish Data Protection Agency (AEPD) came into effect, requiring EUT, as the owner of the Sharework website, to implement an additional cookies banner. This banner provides users with the option to choose which non-necessary cookies to install. To align with this updated regulation, effective from October 31st, 2020, web analytics have been restricted to users who accept analytic cookies. This ensures compliance with the regulatory framework while allowing for a more personalized user experience based on individual preferences regarding the use of non-essential cookies.

In adherence to the new regulation, web analytics have been limited to users who accept this specific type of cookies. It's estimated that this compliance measure has led to a reduction of approximately 60% in the tracking of website traffic analytics. Consequently, the impact of the project website goes beyond the statistics recorded through Matomo analytics and presented in

this deliverable. The actual reach and influence of the website may be more substantial than reflected in the analytics due to the limitations imposed by the user acceptance of certain cookies.

3.2.3 Social Media

Eurecat has taken charge of managing Fatigue4Light's social media presence, overseeing the project's Twitter channel (@Fatigue4Light), the LinkedIn profile and the YouTube channel. Additionally, project partners have actively participated in amplifying project visibility by sharing information on their respective corporate and personal social media accounts, which may include platforms such as Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter or Instagram.

The typology of content published in social media accounts has included:

- Dissemination of project meetings, reviews, milestones, events organised, etc.
- Coverage of project partners participation and attendance in sectorial fairs, conferences and congresses.
- Content curation: news about the automotive industry, Electric Vehicles research, lightweight mobility, numerical simulation approaches, etc.
- News about Fatigue4Light-cluster projects and related initiatives.
- Latest news and results about the project.

3.2.3.1 Twitter

Fatigue4Light launched its Twitter account to raise awareness about the advantages and potential impacts of the project to electric vehicles industry, automotive sector and society in general. In addition, it aims to promote the project's main outcomes to both key stakeholders and a wider audience. For a more detailed on account management and content strategy refer to **D10.1. Project Launch and Communication and Dissemination Plan**.

The content published featured regular incorporation of specific hashtags to enhance tweet visibility, along with mentions of pertinent Twitter accounts, such as partners, event profiles, sister projects, or those associated with related initiatives, especially when sharing news or updates about them.

The Fatigue4Light Twitter profile has been continuously updated with the publication of project news, consortium meetings, videos, promotional materials, and research and milestones achieved, as well as third party content on electric vehicles, lightweight materials, automotive and related projects and initiatives.

During the first years of the project's execution the content strategy was based on publishing generic posts about the Fatigue4Light topics and content curation. Once results started to be ready and public, the content was more focused on communicating the developments, the presence of Fatigue4Light partners at events and webinars organised by the project among other aspects. In order to promote specific events/campaigns, tweets have also incorporated some graphical material and visual elements designed specially to make them more appealing.

Figure 18: Examples of banners optimised for Twitter for promoting specific project's events

Figure 19: Examples of banners optimised for Twitter for promoting the final conference of the project

3.2.3.1.1 Twitter Analytics

The Fatigue4Light Twitter account has garnered a substantial following within the research and industry community due to its active engagement. Since its publication, the account has achieved relevant metrics with over **1,226 likes**, **422 retweets** and **more than 103 mentions**, showcasing a positive response and interaction from its audience.

Through strategic follow-back initiatives and efforts to boost Fatigue4Light's follower profile, the account has successfully amassed more than 150 followers. This diverse group includes automotive and mobility professionals, researchers, PhD and postdoc students specialising in related fields, policy makers, and related initiatives/projects.

Table 12: Fatigue4Light Twitter analytics (M1 – M36, 30th of January)

Fatigue4Light Twitter account	M1 – M36
Posts published	680
Followers	162
Impressions	72,151
Mentions	103
Likes	1,226
Retweets	422

3.2.3.2 LinkedIn

As explained in previous deliverables, LinkedIn has been used as a platform for the interaction among professionals allowing the project to connect with the industrial and academic community, as well as engage with EV automotive stakeholders.

The content published, less frequent than in Twitter, has been based on project news, events participated and organised, scientific articles produced, and milestones achieved, among others. Following the strategy executed for Fatigue4Light Twitter, the project’s LinkedIn account included specific hashtags to increase the post visibility and impact, together with mentions of partners accounts and relevant profiles.

Figure 20: Examples of banners optimised for LinkedIn for promoting the community of interest

3.2.3.2.1 LinkedIn Analytics

The active involvement of the Fatigue4Light LinkedIn account has led to a significant following within the academia and industry community. Since its launch, the account has gained more than 360 followers and more than 250 publications achieving a total of 2,804 likes, 61K impressions and 298 shares.

Table 13: Fatigue4Light LinkedIn analytics (M1 – M36, 30th of January)

Fatigue4Light LinkedIn profile	M1 – M36
Posts published	253
Followers / Connections	362
Impressions	61,581
Likes	2,804
Shares	298

3.2.3.3 YouTube

The Fatigue4Light YouTube channel was created to serve as a content repository of all audiovisual content produced and following the European Commission recommendations mentioning the importance of audiovisual materials to bring the results of the research projects to the general public.

All the videos created during the project were being embedded on the project website audiovisual materials page (<https://fatigue4light.eu/audiovisual-materials/>) and also shared on social media networks for a greater impact.

Figure 21: View of Fatigue4Light YouTube channel

At M36 (end of the project), **21 videos have been published** in the YouTube channel, accumulating a total of **1,427 views**, **7,900 impressions**, **44.6 watch time hours** and **10 subscribers**.

Figure 22: Fatigue4Light YouTube Analytics

Top viewed videos include the animated video showcasing the Fatigue4Light concept, followed by videos on the project’s research, webinars participated and some partners’ interviews.

1		Fatigue4Light Project 25 may 2022	0:54 (58,0 %)	465
2		Fatigue4Light - Hybrid Manufacturing of a 3D-Shaped Fiber Metal Laminate 27 sept 2023	0:38 (47,0 %)	137
3		Fatigue4Light & REVOLUTION webinar 19 abr 2023	5:26 (3,8 %)	124
4		Interview - Michele Maria Tedesco, Metals Material Manager, Stellantis's CRF r... 5 dic 2023	1:12 (56,5 %)	100
5		Interview - Erik Olsson, Associate Professor, Luleå University of Technology 5 dic 2023	0:59 (44,5 %)	88

Figure 23: View of the top 5 most viewed videos. The first column offers data on the average visualisation time while the second one includes the number of visualisations per video.

3.2.3.4 Partners social media accounts

Every partner has actively disseminated Fatigue4Light news and results through both personal and corporate social media networks, including mainly Twitter, LinkedIn, and Facebook. This dissemination efforts includes sharing press releases, events notices, promotional materials, videos, scientific production, and other content published on www.fatigue4light.eu or project's social media accounts.

From M1 – M36, partners collectively contributed to the publication of more than **35 posts on their respective corporate social media accounts**. These posts have received over **513 likes and 70 shares**, indicating a significant level of engagement. For an exhaustive list of partner accounts available for dissemination purposes, please refer to D10.1.

CIMNE @cimne · Dec 13, 2023

Why use numerical methods for fatigue analysis?

@CIMNE's Sergio Jiménez, @Fatigue4Light coordinator, explains how this European project integrates numerical techniques to promote lightweight materials in Electric Vehicles 🚗🔋

youtube.com
Interview - Sergio Jiménez, Associate professor and
In this interview, Sergio Jiménez, project's coordinator and Associate professor at CIMNE, ...

ArcelorMittal Europe
39,466 seguidores
21 horas · Editado

Delighted and proud to be part of this partnership and we are looking forward to continuing to work together to reduce the weight of wheels thanks to #steel.

✅ win-win ✅ It is important to notice that the #carbonfootprint of a steel wheel is strongly related to the carbon footprint of the steel production, thus, a weight reduction achieved through the use of less material for each wheel is directly reflected in a similar reduction of the product carbon footprint.

The #Fatigue4Light project is developing lightweight solutions adapted to the chassis parts of #ElectricVehicles to enhance weight reduction compared to current solutions and increase vehicles' safety.

UNE Asociación Española de Normalización @NormasUNE · Sep 15

Fruto de la labor de normalización de UNE en el proyecto europeo @Fatigue4Light, el 22/09 se celebrará la reunión de lanzamiento de un Workshop @Standards4EU para fijar una metodología de ensayo que determine el límite de fatiga en tiempos + cortos, con un nº reducido de probetas

1 1 2 107

#smartersteelsforpeopleandplanet

CLN CLN spa | CLN Group
4,373 seguidores
1 día

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MW Romania carries out a successful prototyping as part of Fatigue4Light | CLN Group

eurecat @Eurecat_news · Feb 8

Inici del projecte @Fatigue4Light que desenvoluparà nous mètodes de computació per predir el comportament del xassís i seleccionar els materials més indicats per tal d'incrementar-ne l'autonomia i en el que participen també @cimne i la @la_UPC bit.ly/3p7Wp2F

UNE Asociación Española de Normalización and INEA

7 12

Profilglass S.P.A.
6,747 seguidores
3 semanas · Editado

Orgogliosi di far parte del consorzio europeo Fatigue4Light project.

Un'occasione importante per mettere a disposizione del futuro dell'automotive la nostra competenza sull'alluminio.

Scopri di più: <https://lnkd.in/g/XIGg8t>

#weareprofilglass #automotive #alluminio

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Figure 24: Examples of some social media posts published by partners featuring Fatigue4Light

3.2.4 Promotional materials

Throughout the project, a suite of **promotional materials**, including an infosheet, trifold, rollup, a general presentation, a poster layout, and a poster, was crafted. These materials have been regularly updated upon partners' needs, to be used in dissemination activities. Moreover, to ensure accessibility, all the public materials have been conveniently accessible through the project website at <https://fatigue4light.eu/project-materials/>, as well as shared through the social media channels and uploaded in the internal SharePoint folder.

To consult all the Fatigue4Light promotional materials you can refer to **D10.1 Project Launch and Communication and Dissemination Plan** and **D10.4 Interim plan of Use and Dissemination of Results (PUDR)**.

3.2.4.1 Project videos

As mentioned in **Section 3.2.3.3. YouTube**, a total of **21 videos** related Fatigue4Light were published during the project's execution. Of these, 13 have been produced by partners and 5 are from partners' participation in events.

The videos produced include quotes with partners, videos on research outputs, an animated video of Fatigue4Light, and videos on webinars and events organised under the framework of the project.

3.2.4.1.1 Fatigue4Light general video

An informative conceptual video about Fatigue4Light was produced in motion graphics describing the project's main objectives and expected benefits.

Figure 25: View of Fatigue4Light animated video (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=oFloJfbPZkc>)

3.2.4.1.2 Cluster video

As part of the EnLight EVs European cluster, created in collaboration with EU projects and the Horizon Results Booster Service, a video was created to explain the projects forming the cluster, as well as its main objectives and expected outcomes and contribution to the sector and the society at large.

Figure 26: View of EnLight EVs cluster video (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9TLCFoyUd4o>)

3.2.4.1.3 Video interviews with partners

Six video interviews were produced with partners focused on specific topics related to the Fatigue4Light project.

- What is the Fatigue4Light project (CIMNE)
- Advanced Fatigue Testing (EUT)
- Numerical simulation for fatigue prediction (CIMNE)
- Effect of manufacturing on fatigue (LTU)
- Long-life eco-design for Electric Vehicles (EUT)
- Lightweighting analysis in Fatigue4Light (CRF)
- End-of-life and recyclability challenges of Fatigue4Light (RISE)

Figure 27: Some examples of partners interviews videos

3.2.4.1.4 Final video

A final video compiling the results of the project and combining partners interviews together with resource images produced by the consortium and other stock images representing the Fatigue4Light topics, developments, tests, methodologies and other aspects of the project.

Figure 28: View of the Fatigue4Light final video (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jYKmYxd-Tdq&t=1s>)

3.2.4.1.5 Research outputs

- **Fatigue4Light - Hybrid Manufacturing of a 3D-Shaped Fiber Metal Laminate (RISE):** introducing the manufacturing of a multi-material solution for a lower control arm made of hybrid Fiber reinforced polymer-Metal Laminate (FML) as demonstrator.

3.2.4.1.6 Events organised

Four videos have been produced and published showcasing Fatigue4Light webinars organised from M1-M36.

- Webinar: “EVs lightweighting assessment based on AI machine learning and numerical modelling using new materials”, organised in collaboration with REVOLUTION project (April 2023) – [Link here](#)
- EnLight EVs webinar organised within the EU Green Week “Towards a more sustainable mobility through the implementation of advanced solutions and lightweight materials in Electric Vehicles” (June 2023) – [Link here](#)
- Fatigue4Light webinar “Lightweight materials deployment in Electric Vehicles chassis parts” (October 2023) – [Link here](#)
- Fatigue4Light webinar “Advanced Fatigue Simulation methodology for Electric Vehicles chassis parts” (November 2023) – [Link here](#)
- Fatigue4Light webinar “Driving sustainability: eco-design and Life Cycle Assessment approaches for Electric Vehicles” (January 2024) – [Link here](#)

3.2.4.1.7 Events attended

Five videos showcasing partners participation and presentations in different key European and national events were published in the Fatigue4Light YouTube account.

- [Presentation of Fatigue4Light during a webinar on Life Cycle Assessment applications \(February 2023\)](#)
- [Fatigue4Light presentation in the RTR European Conference celebrated in Brussels \(February 2023\)](#)
- [Presentation of Fatigue4Light during Sweden's first test bed for sustainable composite manufacturing \(March 2023\)](#)
- [Dissemination of the project in an industrial workshop organised by three RFCS European projects \(June 2023\)](#)
- [Fatigue4Light presentation in the SALEMA webinar on aluminium for lightweight & sustainable mobility \(October 2023\)](#)

4. Annexes

4.1 Dissemination & Communication KPIs

Table 14: Fatigue4Light Communication and Dissemination KPIs (Data retrieved on January 30th)

Strategy	Indicator	Means of verification	M36	Target to be achieved
Website	Number of website visits	Website Analytics	3,936	>3,500
	Number of pages viewed		10,891	>10,000
	Number of users		2,134	>1,500
	Average session time		5,19 min	>1 min
Social Media	Twitter: Number of followers	Twitter Analytics	162	>100
	Twitter: Number of tweets		680	>150
	Twitter: Twitter impressions		72,151	>30,000
	Twitter: Likes on tweets		1,226	>50
	Twitter: Retweets		422	>30
	Twitter: Mentions		103	>20
	YouTube: Number of videos uploaded	YouTube Analytics	21	>2
	YouTube: Number of video views		1,427	>300
	LinkedIn: Number of followers	LinkedIn Analytics	362	>80
	LinkedIn: Number of posts		253	>40
	LinkedIn: LinkedIn impressions		61,581	>5,000
	Partners: Social media posts about Fatigue4Light		Proof in dissemination reports	37
	Number of press releases		5	>2

Press Releases	Articles published in EU outlets	Proof in dissemination reports / project meetings	23	>20
Events	Number of events participated (congresses, conferences, etc.)	Proof in dissemination reports / project meetings	23	>20
	Final event		1	1
	Number of workshops and webinars organised		6	3
Publications	Number of scientific publications	Proof in dissemination reports / project meetings	15	>6
	Number of articles in specialised magazines / outlets		7	3
Promotional Materials	Audio-visual materials	Proof in dissemination reports / project meetings	21	>10
	Number of roll-ups		1	1
	Number of brochures		1	1
	Poster layout		1	1

4.2 List of articles published in general and specialised online and printed media

Table 15: Media clipping (M1 – M36)

Date	Media	Title	Type	Audience	Economic Value	Link
30/02/24	SETRAM – Automotive Logistics	Proyecto europeo reduce un 40% el peso de los vehículos eléctricos	Online	1000	NA	Link
30/02/24	Posventa	Investigadores logran disminuir el peso de vehículos eléctricos un 40%	Online	1000	NA	Link
20/11/23	DirectIndustry e-Magazine	The New Aluminium Recycling Technology that can boost Europe's EV Industry	Online	1000	NA	Link
03/05/23	Interempresas - Deformación metálica y chapa	Nuevas metodologías avanzadas de ensayo para el óptimo diseño y aplicación de materiales metálicos de alto rendimiento	Online	1000	NA	Link
13/04/23	Vehicle Dynamics International	Eurecat joins Fatigue4Light project to reduce EV chassis weight	Online	NA	NA	Link
01/08/22	Fulls d'Enginyeria	Els reptes de tota la cadena de valor de l'automoció	Online	NA	NA	Link
17/02/22	El Periódico Catalunya	La UPC, Eurecat i MSX opten a dirigir l'FP del motor a Martorell	Print	23700	23,189.58€	Link
17/02/22	El Periódico Espanya	La UPC, Eurecat y MSX optan a dirigir la FP del motor en Martorell	Print	23700	23,189.58€	Link
16/02/22	El Periódico Espanya	MSX, Eurecat y la UPC, candidatos finales a gestionar el centro de FP de Martorell	Online	890434	8,458.16€	Link
16/02/22	El Periódico Catalunya	MSX, Eurecat i la UPC, candidats finals a gestionar el centre d'FP de Martorell	Online	890434	8,458.16€	Link
16/09/21	Automotive manufacturing Solutions	Stress test: new modelling approach for component fatigue testing	Online	NA	NA	Link
01/05/21	Interempresas – Automoción	Eurecat participa en un proyecto para reducir el peso del chasis de vehículos eléctricos	Print	1000	1,460.00€	Link
01/04/21	La Tribuna de Automoción	Eurecat se incorpora el proyecto Fatigue4Light	Print	1000	1377.77€	Link
01/04/21	Canal Taronja – Butlletí	Eurecat participa en un projecte de més de 5,5 milions d'euros per reduir el pes del xassís de vehicles elèctrics	Print	NA	NA	Link
28/02/21	Americal Industrial Magazine	Eurecat participa en un proyecto para reducir el chasis de vehículos eléctricos	Online	NA	NA	Link
28/02/21	Izaro	Eurecat trabaja en Fatigue4Light, que busca reducir el peso del chasis de vehículos eléctricos	Online	1000	30€	Link
26/02/21	Interempresas - Automoción	Eurecat participa en un proyecto para reducir el peso del chasis de vehículos eléctricos	Online	9223	442.75€	Link

26/02/21	30 Virtual	Eurecat participa en un projecte de més de 5,5 milions d'euros per reduir el pes del xassís de vehicles elèctrics	Online	1000	30€	Link
26/02/21	30 Virtual	Eurecat participa en un proyecto de más de 5,5 millones de euros para reducir el peso del chasis de vehículos eléctricos	Online	1000	30€	Link
25/02/21	Consorci de Formació Professional d'Automoció - Generalitat de Catalunya	Eurecat participará en el projecte Fatigue4Light per impulsar el vehicle elèctric	Online	NA	NA	Link
25/02/21	FEMA 4.0 Industria Sostenible	Eurecat participa en el proyecto Fatigue4Light para el desarrollo de vehículos eléctricos	Online	NA	NA	Link
25/02/21	Factoría del Futuro	Eurecat participa en el proyecto Fatigue4Light para el desarrollo de vehículos eléctricos	Online	1000	30€	Link
24/02/21	Metallindustria	Eurecat participa en un proyecto para reducir el peso del chasis de vehículos eléctricos	Online	1000	30€	Link
18/02/21	Politecnico di Torino Magazine	Ridurre il peso dei veicoli: al via il progetto Fatigue4Light	Online	NA	NA	Link
06/02/21	La Vanguardia	Eurecat pren carretera	Print	436000	18.770,94€	Link